

Co-Creating Circular
Resource Flows in Cities

constRuctive mEtabolic processes For materiaL fIOWs in
urban and peri-urban environments across Europe

Deliverable 2.6

Multi-Platform Release of REFLOW OS for Cloud & Embedded Infrastructure

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1 Introduction

1.1 About REFLOW

REFLOW is an EU Horizon 2020 research project running from 2019-2022, which aimed to enable the transition of European cities towards circular and regenerative practices. More specifically, REFLOW used Fab Labs and makerspaces as catalysers of a systemic change in urban and peri-urban environments, which enable, visualize and regulate “four freedoms”: free movement of materials, people, (technological) knowledge and commons, in order to reduce materials consumption, maximize multifunctional use of (public) spaces and envisage regenerative practices. The project provided best practices aligning market and government needs in order to create favourable conditions for the public and private sectors to adopt circular economy (CE) practices. REFLOW created new CE business models within six pilot cities: Amsterdam, Berlin, Cluj-Napoca, Milan, Paris and Vejle, and assessed their social, environmental and economic impact and enabled active citizen involvement and systemic change to re-think the current approach to material flows in cities.

1.2 Reflow Vision

A circular and regenerative city in REFLOW represents an urban system with social and business practices which place equal attention to **social, environmental and economic impact**; where **technology** is open and represents a central enabler of positive social and environmental change; where the urban system ensures and support resilience of social and ecological systems; where **governance** is collaborative and inclusive; where **knowledge** is shared, and **stakeholders** are active and involved.

1.3 About the Deliverable

This deliverable reports on the work done in the scope of technical development, implementation and deployment of the REFLOW OS component of Work Package 2 “IT Infrastructure & Tools”. The focus of this report is to document the technical architecture, integration and release of REFLOW OS components and their APIs as well as to outline cloud to embedded hybrid component multi-platform deployment scenarios.

1.4 Structure of the Report

The deliverable starts with an overview of the core ReflowOS system architecture components & their data flows in section 2. Section 3 goes on to describe basic data object structures and protocols and methods available to manipulate them. Section 4 details specific APIs, data objects and extensions to ReflowOS infrastructure to facilitate generation of material passports, the validation of material passports together with their submission to a blockchain. Section 5 and 6 documents ReflowOS installation procedures and offers conclusions over flexible multi-platform deployment strategies. The appendices document the APIs and data objects in detail.

1.5 Relation to Other Tasks

Figure 1 illustrates the REFLOW Framework

Within the context of the REFLOW Framework developed in REFLOW deliverable D1.3, the multi-platform release of ReflowOS itself represents a release phase within the Product and Tech Innovation framework level. In particular, this release phase has been supported by continuous feedback with the work carried out in WP5,

especially working closely with the coordination, development and implementation work carried out in T5.4 REFLOW Pilot Applications. The Material Flow Analysis work carried out in T5.3 assisted the implementation of pilot modelling within the Valueflows ontology and ultimately lead to improvements of the emerging standard itself.

1.6 List of Abbreviations & Keywords

ActivityPub	ActivityPub is a standard for the Internet in the Social Web Networking Group of the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C).
API	Application Programming Interface
Back-end	Data access layer of a piece of software, mostly a web application in contrast to the presentation layer or front-end
CI	Continuous Integration
EconomicEvent	An observed event in the economic flow in the Valueflows vocabulary that reflects a change in an economic resource
EconomicResource	An asset, including a material resource, in the Valueflows vocabulary
FQDN	Fully Qualified Domain Name, a canonical form of an Internet hostname
Front-end	Front-end is the client-side or web design in the web industry
GUI or UI	(Graphic) User Interface
GraphQL	A graph data query and manipulation language for APIs
Intents	Intents represent potential future Valueflows actions. For example, offers and needs are types of Valueflows Intents
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation , a standard data interchange format that uses human-readable text to

	exchange and store data.
Material Passport	A cryptographically signed trace of all the events a material resource has gone through (a resource's history), including actors and other processes, events & resources present in those events.
Network Metabolism	Any economic event stored in ReflowOS can be analyzed in relation to previous or following events - the more activities performed and stored, the more data is available for shaping and studying emergent flows that help define the aggregate network metabolism.
ODD	Open Data Dashboard, the open data visualization component of ReflowOS
SBC	Single Board Computer
Valueflows	A set of common vocabularies to describe flows of economic resources of all kinds within distributed economic ecosystems. As a common standard, it assists interoperability across diverse software projects. It is based on the REA (Resource, Event, Agent) economic model.

2. System Architecture

ReflowOS is an operating system for circular cities - a collection of tools designed to promote, assist and incentivise circular practices in local ecosystems by monitoring and optimising urban metabolic processes among participants. The key enabling features of ReflowOS are explained in detail in the REFLOW deliverable D2.2 Architecture and Manual for Distributed Network Setup and Maintenance, which also reflected in its living website¹.

The core of ReflowOS system architecture consists of three constituent parts, namely the:

- ReflowOS Front End – WeLoop (as well as other UIs, clients & embedded IoT applications)
- Open Data Dashboard – an open dataset visualisation analysis system
- ReflowOS Back End – the ReflowOS Server

¹ <https://reflowos.dyne.org/>

ReflowOS front end clients can be developed and deployed for a variety of functionalities to support the individual needs of each circular city's use case. In the context of the REFLOW project, WeLoop is the first ReflowOS front end client developed and is designed to be an extensible Graphical UI for a material marketplace for the circular exchange of materials to be tailored and adapted for individual use cases.

The Open Data Dashboard, together with other open data set import and analysis functionalities, acts as a ReflowOS client to serve as a dissemination tool rendering visual information and analytic insights into the circular city.

Figure 2 illustrates the communication paths and transport protocols used between the core components of a single deployed ReflowOS instance

2.1 ReflowOS Client Front Ends

2.1.1 WeLoop

WeLoop is the first client web application developed for ReflowOS. It is a modular front-end framework intended to be used as a base for Reflow pilots to develop their own ReflowOS front end interfaces customised for their unique business use cases.

WeLoop is developed in the React/Typescript development environment. It uses the Apollo GraphQL library and provides a UI library and example style guide for consistent further development by REFLOW pilots for their specific use case requirements.

Figure 3 illustrates WeLoop rendering a detailed history for a Material Passport

Detailed WeLoop installation, operation & functionality is described in Reflow project deliverable D2.5 Reflow OS Graphical Interfaces submitted in M28.

For a detailed description of the use of the ReflowOS WeLoop UI client application within REFLOW pilot use cases, see REFLOW deliverable D5.4 Reflow Pilot Applications.

The code repository for WeLoop ReflowOS client application (including installation instructions) is available on the REFLOW Project Github resource at <https://github.com/reflow-project/weloop/>

2.1.2 Phoenix UI

The Phoenix UI is a simple proof-of-concept client web application developed and included within the ReflowOS server and also includes GraphiQL², a low-level GraphQL client used by developers to debug and test functionality sets such as portable JSON data object management, material passport generation and networked federation validation.

The Phoenix UI is developed in the Elixir programming language using the Phoenix web framework with LiveView and Surface for UI components and views, and utilises the Absinthe GraphQL library.

Figure 4 illustrates creating a Valueflows process in the Phoenix UI ReflowOS client

For a detailed description of the use of the ReflowOS Phoenix UI client application within the REFLOW project pilot use cases, see REFLOW deliverable D5.4 Reflow Pilot Applications submitted in M34.

The source code repository for the Phoenix ReflowOS client application is available on the REFLOW Project Github resource at <https://github.com/reflow-project/bonfire-app>.

2.2 Open Data Dashboard

The Open Data Dashboard (ODD) is a tool to visualise the data gathered and processed by the individual REFLOW pilots. Its capabilities includes, for example, the depiction of resource consumption over time, map

² <https://graphql-dotnet.github.io/docs/getting-started/graphiql/>

visualisations to display location-specific resource potentials, and bar charts to visualise the amount of saved resources and Sankey diagrams to emphasise the looping character of specific resource flows.

2.2.1 Open Data Dashboard Architecture

The ODD is subdivided into two main components:

- the Connector Bridge, which provides the infrastructure necessary to ingest data from the pilot's endpoint to Apache Superset; and
- Apache Superset³ itself, which is responsible for rendering the data visualisation.

When a specific pilot use case utilises a ReflowOS server, regular data ingestion functionality will be provided by the Connector at predefined time intervals pulling the data from the ReflowOS server and pushing it into Apache Superset's database. If no ReflowOS server is implemented for the pilot use case data source, then the ODD GraphQL API can be utilised by the pilot to directly push data into Apache Superset's database.

³ <https://superset.apache.org/>

Figure 5 illustrates the component data flows of the Open Data Dashboard

2.2.2 ODD Connector

Figure 6 illustrates the detailed data flows of the ODD Connector

The ODD Connector automatically pulls data updates from the respective pilot data source and pushes it into the database of Apache Superset. It is a modular system consisting of four different components, namely: Scheduler, Importer, Transformer, and Exporter.

The Scheduler-Trigger is the one exposed to the outside. The endpoint of the Scheduler is the only one that should be externally addressed to trigger a data-harvesting process initially.

The Scheduler⁴ expects predefined triggers to be passed as an argument inside the request body together with the PipeName of the PipeObject corresponding to the harvesting process to be triggered. The trigger initializes a new harvesting process that updates the ODD SQL Server, making the updated data available for visualization by Apache Superset. When addressed by the client (step 1) it clones the Pipe Git Repository⁵

⁴ The ODD Scheduler repository is found at <https://github.com/reflow-project/odd-scheduler>

⁵ The ODD Pipe Git Repository is found at <https://github.com/reflow-project/odd-harvesting-pipes>

(step 2), selects the PipeObject corresponding to the PipeName provided by the client and sends it to the Importer via HTTPS (step 3). The JSON PipeObject contains all relevant harvesting process information, including the endpoint providing the data, the endpoints of all of the Connector's components, and the table's name to be created inside the ODD SQL Server. Each table within the ODD SQL Server represents one PipeObject. All PipeObjects are stored in a git repository, whose URI is provided as an environment variable parameter for the Scheduler.

The Importer⁶ sends the GraphQL query contained within the PipeObject to the ReflowOS GraphQL Client API of the respective ReflowOS server specified within the PipeObject (step 4). It then writes the resulting data into the PipeObject and sends it to the Transformer via HTTPS (step 5).

The Transformer⁷ clones the Transformation Script Git Repository⁸ configured within the PipeObject (step 6) and transforms the data into a form suitable for SQL injection according to the specific transformation script configured within the PipeObject. The transformed data is then written into the PipeObject and sent to all Exporters via HTTPS (step 7).

The Exporters receive the PipeObject from the Transformer and directly injects the transformed data into the specified database within the ODD SQL Server via the (step 8).

As shown in the figure above, there are multiple Exporters, each of which corresponds to each pilot use case. This is a design choice rooted in the decision that there are multiple databases within the ODD SQL Server, one for each specific pilot use case. Each Exporter can only operate on a single database, whose URI and credentials are provided as environment variables when initialising each Exporter. An Exporter endpoint is contained within the PipeObject which routes the corresponding data to the correct database.

The ODD GraphQL API is a simple GraphQL API dedicated to a single Cluj Pilot use case and offers one POST request to ingest new data into the ODD SQL Server. Smart-meter data is being provided by the client in JSON format inside the request body and sent to the ODD GraphQL API via HTTPS. The API creates the corresponding SQL statements and injects them into the ODD SQL Server.

The full details of the ODD Scheduler API is listed in the Appendix section ODD Piveau Scheduler API. The JSON template for the PipeObject is listed in the Appendix section ODD PipeObject JSON Template.

2.2.3 ODD Apache Superset

The ODD Apache Superset front end runs as a web-based data visualisation and analysis tool. The data imported by the Connector can be queried, transformed and visualised via its UI. Each pilot has one or multiple dashboards dedicated to it. Below are some example graph outputs of pilot ReflowOS Open Data Dashboards:

⁶ The ODD Importer repository is found at <https://github.com/reflow-project/odd-importer>

⁷ The ODD Transformer repository is found at <https://github.com/reflow-project/odd-transformer>

⁸ The ODD Transformation Script repository is found at <https://github.com/reflow-project/odd-transformation-scripts>

Figure 7 Figure represents a cut-out of the Reflow Amsterdam Zorgshorten dashboard, emphasizing the cleaning of medical gowns after their use in a hospital

Figure 8 shows a cutout of the Berlin Pilot Open Data Dashboard, which represents available location-specific heating potential on a map, with overall utilised potential and available min and max potential

Figure 9 shows a cutout of the Cluj Pilot Open Data Dashboard, which compares the respective plants' power consumption to emphasise visually the benefit of implemented energy-saving measures

Detailed information documenting REFLOW pilot use of the Open Data Dashboard is contained within REFLOW deliverable 5.4 Reflow Pilot Applications.

2.3 ReflowOS Server Back End

The ReflowOS server is based on the open-source Bonfire federated application framework⁹. It is implemented in the Elixir programming language¹⁰, built upon the Erlang virtual machine, and designed to develop highly reliable, resilient and scalable systems. It uses the Absinthe GraphQL Toolkit to deliver a GraphQL Client API, and it implements the W3C ActivityPub¹¹ standard to deliver server-to-server federation.

A ReflowOS server consists of the following components:

- a ReflowOS server
- a PostgreSQL database for a local data store
- a filestore for uploaded files
- a Meili search index

⁹ <https://github.com/bonfire-networks>

¹⁰ <https://elixir-lang.org/>

¹¹ <https://activitypub.rocks/>

Figure 10 illustrates the data flows within ReflowOS server components within a ReflowOS deployment

2.3.1 ReflowOS GraphQL Client API

The Reflow OS server provides a flexible GraphQL API for client applications flexible enough to satisfy a wide range of use cases and client application requirements.

For example, the ReflowOS GraphQL API provides for client applications by supporting front end graphical user interfaces such as WeLoop and the Phoenix UI, but also supports the Open Data Dashboard component for data visualisation, as well as embedded automated client application for automatic data transactions not requiring a web-based human interface.

The client applications developed by the Reflow pilots demonstrate the capacity of the Reflow OS GraphQL Client API to support a wide diversity of client application development environments and platforms for circular activities – from Telegram instant messaging bots to bespoke open-source embedded WiFi data input devices.

The ReflowOS GraphQL Client API is used extensively by an impressive array of client applications in Reflow pilot use cases documented in the Reflow deliverable D5.4 REFLOW Pilot Applications submitted in M34.

The full ReflowOS GraphQL Client API is documented in the Appendix in section ReflowOS APIs

2.4 Federation of ReflowOS Servers

A federated ReflowOS server communicates to other ReflowOS servers via ActivityPub, a W3C standard messaging protocol that forms the backbone of the peer-to-peer federated Internet network collection of services often referred to as the Fediverse¹². Other popular messaging applications within the Fediverse include Mastodon (a decentralised Twitter-like messaging application) and PeerTube (a decentralised YouTube-like service).

The ActivityPub protocol allows each server to route its messages in a peer-to-peer fashion via each server's unique fully qualified domain name (FQDN) in the global Internet Domain Name System (DNS) in a similar way that Internet email is routed and delivered to the correct email servers of each domain.

ReflowOS server data objects are encapsulated in ActivityPub messages and exchanged between each federated server.

¹² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fediverse>

Figure 11 illustrates the communication paths and transport protocols used between federated instances of ReflowOS server deployments

Each local ReflowOS server stores all authoritative data for its local data objects including user agents and economic resources, as well as economic events and processes.

When federated activity occurs, a local instance is populated with referential data gathered through external interactions across the network with remote data objects referenced uniquely through their fully qualified name identifier.

Figure 12 demonstrates when federated workflow activity occurs, that each local ReflowOS database is populated with referential data to other participating ReflowOS federated instances

Each item in a local Reflow database and search index always refers back to the originating instance for the full data (e.g.: remote actors, economic events and processes, as well as economic resources - their current status, quantities and/or balances).

The infrastructural prerequisites for ReflowOS server federation are that:

- the server is reachable from a unique globally routed IP address over TCP port 443
- the server has a unique consistent fully qualified domain name (FQDN) that maps to the IP address
- a TLS certificate corresponding to the FQDN is configured to be presented over HTTPS on TCP/IP port 443 of the interface the server binds to (or a reverse HTTPS proxy to offload TLS handling)

3. Data Object Structures & Manipulation Methods

3.1 ReflowOS & Valueflows

A ReflowOS server stores, manipulates and routes Valueflows data objects, exposing the data objects as JSON for interoperability and portability.

Valueflows¹³ is a standard set of ontologies representing a REA (Resource, Event, Agent) economic model. Within the Valueflows vocabulary, there are three defined levels of differing relationships of REA (resources, events, agents) elements, being defined as Knowledge (what is known), Planning (what will be done), and Observations (what has been done).

Figure 13 shows the three core levels of Valueflows data objects and their relationship between the present, future & past

Figure 14 illustrates a set of selected elements within the three core levels of the Valueflows ontology

There are relationships between the levels. Knowledge gives recipes of how things can or should be done (according to best practice and recognised standards for example). Plans outline what is intended to be done and how it is to be done. Observations record what has been done to which resource(s) by which Agent(s). Observations can reference plans, processes and specifications related to the observed event. Processes are Valueflows container elements of one or more Economic Event elements.

¹³ <https://valueflo.ws>

Figure 15 illustrates graph relationships between Valueflows entities

ReflowOS represents material flows of resources as a graph structure of all Valueflows resources, events, processes and agents as JSON data objects.

For a full up to date description of Valueflows object elements, refer to the Valueflows web-site at <https://www.valueflo.ws>.

3.2 ReflowOS Valueflows JSON data objects

3.2.1 Agent JSON Object Example

ReflowOS represents all user accounts as Valueflow Agent JSON structures.

```
[
  {
    "displayUsername": "Gene8936",
    "id": "01FSMS9337TFTFV51V9RBDNFY5",
    "name": "OLVG",
    "note": null
  }
]
```

3.2.2 EconomicResource JSON Object Example

ReflowOS represents all material resources as Valueflows EconomicResource data objects.

```
[
  {
    "__typename": "EconomicResource",
    "accountingQuantity": {
```



```
"hasNumericalValue": 1.0,
"hasUnit": {
  "id": "01FSMS8R9A8DMKVQEY5WZTF4PJ",
  "label": "om2:one",
  "symbol": "#"
}
},
"currentLocation": {
  "alt": 0.0,
  "id": "01FSMS9DYS3H6SP76X315G7DNN",
  "lat": 52.35871773455108,
  "long": 4.916762398221842,
  "mappableAddress": "Oosterpark 9, 1091 AC Amsterdam",
  "name": "OLVG locatie oost",
  "note": "olvg.nl"
},
"id": "01FSMSBAJ3N6NJGA9XBSGTNRT6",
"note": "Clean Lease Schort: 7edc0ee2-6088-43e3-aefb-b5493db1d822",
"onhandQuantity": {
  "hasNumericalValue": 1.0,
  "hasUnit": {
    "id": "01FSMS8R9A8DMKVQEY5WZTF4PJ",
    "label": "om2:one",
    "symbol": "#"
  }
},
"primaryAccountable": {
  "displayUsername": "Gene8936",
  "id": "01FSMS9337TFTFV51V9RBDNFY5",
  "name": "OLVG"
},
"resourceName": "Gown",
"trackingIdentifier": "http://cleanlease.nl/zs/7edc0ee2-6088-43e3-aefb-b5493db1d822"
}
]
```

3.2.3 EconomicEvent JSON Object Example

ReflowOS represents all actions performed on materials as Valueflows EconomicEvents.

```
[
{
  "__typename": "EconomicEvent",
  "action": {
    "id": "produce"
  },
  "effortQuantity": null,
  "id": "01FSMS9MXTGAMQD9TDPPS18QQF",
  "note": "seed pool for a_hospital - 2022-01-17T00:00:00+00:00",
  "provider": {
    "displayUsername": "Gene8936",
    "id": "01FSMS9337TFTFV51V9RBDNFY5",
    "name": "OLVG"
  },
  "receiver": {
    "displayUsername": "Gene8936",
```



```
"id": "01FSMS9337TFTFV51V9RBDNFY5",
"name": "OLVG"
},
"resourceClassifiedAs": [],
"resourceInventoriedAs": {
  "__typename": "EconomicResource",
  "accountingQuantity": {
    "hasNumericalValue": 1.0,
    "hasUnit": {
      "id": "01FSMS8R9A8DMKVQEY5WZTF4PJ",
      "label": "om2:one",
      "symbol": "#"
    }
  }
},
"currentLocation": {
  "alt": 0.0,
  "id": "01FSMS9DYS3H6SP76X315G7DNN",
  "lat": 52.35871773455108,
  "long": 4.916762398221842,
  "mappableAddress": "Oosterpark 9, 1091 AC Amsterdam",
  "name": "OLVG locatie oost",
  "note": "olvg.nl"
},
"id": "01FSMS9K2ASGVMA1Y6KDVKVPZ",
"note": "Clean Lease Schort: 1e76cb48-7e3f-4a37-b42e-cff4921cb26e",
"onhandQuantity": {
  "hasNumericalValue": 1.0,
  "hasUnit": {
    "id": "01FSMS8R9A8DMKVQEY5WZTF4PJ",
    "label": "om2:one",
    "symbol": "#"
  }
},
"primaryAccountable": {
  "displayUsername": "Gene8936",
  "id": "01FSMS9337TFTFV51V9RBDNFY5",
  "name": "OLVG"
},
"resourceName": "Gown",
"trackingIdentifier": "http://cleanlease.nl/zs/1e76cb48-7e3f-4a37-b42e-cff4921cb26e"
},
"resourceQuantity": {
  "hasNumericalValue": 1.0,
  "hasUnit": {
    "id": "01FSMS8R9A8DMKVQEY5WZTF4PJ",
    "label": "om2:one",
    "symbol": "#"
  }
},
"toResourceInventoriedAs": null
}
]
```

3.3 ReflowOS & the Graph Query Language (GraphQL)

GraphQL is an open-source API data query and manipulation language that, unlike a RESTful API, is optimised for and well suited to searching, filtering and manipulating graph data such as ReflowOS Valueflows JSON data objects. GraphQL APIs differ from RESTful APIs in that they offer data minimization by design. For the ReflowOS GraphQL Client API, this property is beneficial for two reasons - firstly, it offers a good privacy by design pattern, as data object elements returned can be managed server-side, and secondly it optimizes network performance, as clients specify only the data elements they require for any particular interaction.

The ReflowOS GraphQL Client API offers the ability to search, filter and manipulate objects and return results in JSON.

For example, the following example GraphQL queries and mutations can be entered into a GraphiQL client interface.

3.3.1 Login

To login to authenticate as a user in GraphiQL:

GraphQL client query submitted to server:

```
mutation {
  login(emailOrUsername: "demo@berlin.zembla", password: "berlin.zembla") {
    currentUser {id}
  }
}
```

JSON returned to client query by GraphQL server:

```
{
  "data": {
    "login": {
      "currentUser": {
        "id": "01FZ6F2XFE5NG1MGN69E7BCNAN"
      }
    }
  }
}
```

3.3.2 Create a ResourceSpecification & Process

Within Valueflows, a ResourceSpecification is a singular lowest level useful type or kind of a resource. Each EconomicResource is an observable manifestation of its ResourceSpecification. Optionally EconomicResources can additionally have any number of associated EconomicClassifications, which also can be used to match, filter & search against.

Secondly, within ReflowOS it is necessary to associate EconomicEvents with a Process object, which in turn facilitates the generation of material passports.

To create a ResourceSpecification and a Process:

GraphQL client query submitted to server:

```
mutation {
  createResourceSpecification(resourceSpecification: {
    name: "rice"
  }) {
    resourceSpecification {id}
  }

  createProcess(process: {
    name: "process for harvesting rice"
  }) {
    process {id}
  }
}
```

JSON returned to client query by GraphQL server:

```
{
  "data": {
    "createProcess": {
      "process": {
        "id": "01FZ6F4G231W28AMFZS02MDVMM"
      }
    },
    "createResourceSpecification": {
      "resourceSpecification": {
        "id": "01FZ6F4FZ3XX1DGM05M42FWZ22"
      }
    }
  }
}
```

3.3.3 Create an EconomicEvent that produces a Resource

Using the created ResourceSpecification and Process, create an EconomicEvent that produces an EconomicResource:

GraphQL client query submitted to server:


```
mutation {
  createEconomicEvent(event: {
    action: "produce"
    outputOf: "01FZ6F4G231W28AMFZS02MDVMM" # process for harvesting rice
    provider: "01FZ6F2XFE5NG1MGN69E7BCNAN" # @demo@berlin.zembla
    receiver: "01FZ6F2XFE5NG1MGN69E7BCNAN" # @demo@berlin.zembla
    resourceConformsTo: "01FZ6F4FZ3XX1DGM05M42FWZ22" # rice
    resourceQuantity: {
      hasNumericalValue: 50
      hasUnit: "01FZ6F4FYF0FPETYZ3DY1GM8M4" # kg
    }
    hasPointInTime: "2022-03-27T22:45:00Z"
  },
  newInventoriedResource: {
    name: "wild rice"
  }) {
  economicEvent {
    id
    provider {id name displayUsername}
    receiver {id name displayUsername}
    resourceQuantity {...measure}
  }
  economicResource { # newly-created resource
    id
    name
    primaryAccountable {id name displayUsername}
    onhandQuantity {...measure}
    accountingQuantity {...measure}
  }
}
}

fragment unit on Unit {id label symbol}
fragment measure on Measure {hasNumericalValue, hasUnit {...unit}}
```

JSON returned to client query by GraphQL server:

```
{
  "data": {
    "createEconomicEvent": {
      "economicEvent": {
        "id": "01FZ6F6E260T1BK9HMNFY8K97",
        "provider": {
          "displayUsername": "@demo_berlin_zembla@reflowos.test",
          "id": "01FZ6F2XFE5NG1MGN69E7BCNAN",
          "name": "AT demo AT berlin DOT zembla"
        },
      },
      "receiver": {
        "displayUsername": "@demo_berlin_zembla@reflowos.test",
        "id": "01FZ6F2XFE5NG1MGN69E7BCNAN",
      },
    },
  },
}
```



```
    "name": "AT demo AT berlin DOT zembla"
  },
  "resourceQuantity": {
    "hasNumericalValue": 50,
    "hasUnit": {
      "id": "01FZ6F4FYF0FPETYZ3DY1GM8M4",
      "label": "kilogram",
      "symbol": "kg"
    }
  }
},
"economicResource": {
  "accountingQuantity": null,
  "id": "01FZ6F6E06WBS1TTFE93PP38HZ",
  "name": "wild rice",
  "onhandQuantity": null,
  "primaryAccountable": {
    "displayUsername": "@demo_berlin_zembla@reflowos.test",
    "id": "01FZ6F2XFE5NG1MGN69E7BCNAN",
    "name": "AT demo AT berlin DOT zembla"
  }
}
}
}
}
```

3.3.4 Create an offer

ReflowOS allows a user to create needs and offers to make available to other participants but also allows each user to search and filter available needs and offers of other participants. Offers and needs are Valueflows Intent data objects that form the core of the network metabolism.¹⁴

To create an offer:

GraphQL client query submitted to server:

```
mutation {
  createOffer(intent: {
    name: "some offer"
    action: "transfer"
    receiver: "01FTAZV86NNEFY3229K1T4AHBN"
    atLocation: "01G1FYHMQBA0474BJJHH771RZ"
    hasBeginning: "2022-01-02T03:04:05Z"
    resourceInventoriedAs: "01FTB03K54ZF38FHEKGVHTWGY8"
    availableQuantity: {
      hasNumericalValue: 25
      hasUnit: "01FTB06BQ64MSS7XSB3QMSW83R"
    }
  })
}
```

¹⁴ for a more detailed explanation of network metabolism, see REFLOW deliverable D2.2, section “Network Metabolism”

```
  }) {  
    intent {  
      id  
      name  
    }  
  }  
}
```

JSON returned to client query by GraphQL server:

```
{  
  "data": {  
    "createOffer": {  
      "intent": {  
        "id": "01G1FYMQCDCVJFB5XZMWE3HKXR",  
        "name": "offer of rice"  
      }  
    }  
  }  
}
```

3.3.5 Search for Offers by Proximity

Searching for offers or needs by proximity can be useful as a means to keep urban metabolism as local as possible (eg. for optimising resilience through choosing local supply chains, etc).

To search for offers contained by proximity:

GraphQL client query submitted to server::

```
query {  
  intents(filter: {geolocation: {nearPoint: {lat: 24, long: 74}, distance: {meters: 7500}}}) {  
    id  
    name  
  }  
}
```

JSON returned to client query by GraphQL server:

```
{  
  "data": {  
    "intents": [  
      {  
        "id": "01G1FYMQCDCVJFB5XZMWE3HKXR",  
        "name": "offer of rice"  
      }  
    ]  
  }  
}
```

For further functional examples of searching, filtering and manipulating ReflowOS Valueflows objects with GraphQL, refer to API Tour, a section of the latest on-line revision of the REFLOW deliverable D2.2 Architecture and Manual for Distributed Network Setup and Maintenance.¹⁵

For full documentation of the API, refer to the Appendix section ReflowOS GraphQL Client API.

4. Data Flow Integrity & Material Passports

4.1 Track and trace

In ReflowOS, tracking and tracing are functions that operate on Valueflows objects such as an EconomicResource ID and provide graph traversals of all related Valueflows economic resources, processes and events (Valueflows elements). Tracking applies this process in a forward graph direction, whilst tracing applies the process in a backward direction.

ReflowOS Valueflows Track & Trace – tracking forward, tracing back

Figure 16 illustrates Track and Trace along material resource flow data objects

For a given flow element, ReflowOS uses the following logic to find Valueflows elements that come after a given Valueflows element (for tracking) or before a given Valueflows element (for tracing).

¹⁵ https://reflowos.dyne.org/docs/api_tour

- For an EconomicResource element:
 - after: EconomicEvents affecting it that are inputs to Processes or transfer/move EconomicEvents with the resource defined as the `resourceInventoriedAs`
 - before: EconomicEvents affecting it that are outputs from Processes or transfer/move EconomicEvents with the resource defined as the `toResourceInventoriedAs`
- For a Process:
 - after: EconomicEvents that are outputs
 - before: EconomicEvents that are inputs
- For an EconomicEvent:
 - after:
 - a Process to which it is an input, or
 - an EconomicResource which it affected as the output of a Process, or
 - if it is a transfer or move event, the EconomicResource labelled `toResourceInventoriedAs`
 - before:
 - a Process from which it is an output, or
 - if it is an input to a Process, the EconomicResource which it affects, or
 - if it is a transfer or move event and the current EconomicResource is the `toResourceInventoriedAs`, then the previous EconomicResource is the `resourceInventoriedAs`

4.1.1 GraphQL Track and Trace Example

For ReflowOS client applications, the ReflowOS server offers Track & Trace functions over the ReflowOS GraphQL API.

The following is a relatively short example of a combined track and trace GraphQL query on a Valueflows EconomicResource object. In this example, the Valueflows EconomicResource ID represents a medical gown from an Amsterdam Pilot use case.

GraphQL client query submitted to server:

```
query {
  economicResource(id: "01FSMSDFVY06V41V6PWWF537A7") {
    ...resource
    trace {...trace}
    track {...track}
  }
}
```

```
fragment spatialThing on SpatialThing {
  id name note mappableAddress alt lat long
}
```



```
fragment unit on Unit {
  id label symbol
}

fragment measure on Measure {
  hasNumericalValue hasUnit {...unit}
}

fragment resourceSpecification on ResourceSpecification {
  id
  name
  note
  defaultUnitOfResource {...unit}
  defaultUnitOfEffort {...unit}
}

fragment process on Process {
  id
  processName: name
  note
  inputs {id}
  outputs {id}
}

fragment event on EconomicEvent {
  id
  note
  hasEnd hasBeginning hasPointInTime
  provider {id name displayUsername note}
  receiver {id name displayUsername note}
  action {id label}
  inputOf {id name}
  outputOf {id name}
  resourceQuantity {...measure}
  effortQuantity {...measure}
  resourceConformsTo {...resourceSpecification}
  resourceInventoriedAs {id name}
  toResourceInventoriedAs {id name}
  atLocation {...spatialThing}
}

fragment resource on EconomicResource {
  id
  name
  note
  primaryAccountable {id name displayUsername note}
  conformsTo {...resourceSpecification}
  accountingQuantity {...measure}
  onhandQuantity {...measure}
  currentLocation {...spatialThing}
  trackingIdentifier
}

fragment trace on ProductionFlowItem {
  __typename
  ... on Process {...process}
  ... on EconomicEvent {...event}
  ... on EconomicResource {...resource}
```



```
}  
  
fragment track on ProductionFlowItem {  
  __typename  
  ... on Process {...process}  
  ... on EconomicEvent {...event}  
  ... on EconomicResource {...resource}  
}
```

Which produces JSON returned to client query by GraphQL server:

```
{  
  "data": {  
    "economicResource": {  
      "accountingQuantity": {  
        "hasNumericalValue": 1,  
        "hasUnit": {  
          "id": "01FSMS8R9A8DMKVQEY5WZTF4PJ",  
          "label": "om2:one",  
          "symbol": "#"  
        }  
      },  
      "conformsTo": null,  
      "currentLocation": {  
        "alt": 0,  
        "id": "01FSMSCEWC1KHKKYE7SN89TQTW",  
        "lat": 51.4722592,  
        "long": 5.4126426,  
        "mappableAddress": "De schakel 30, 5651 Eindhoven",  
        "name": "CleanLease Eindhoven",  
        "note": "Textile service provider"  
      },  
      "id": "01FSMSDFVY06V41V6PWMP537A7",  
      "name": "Gown",  
      "note": "Clean Lease Schort: 53d26bce-66f8-4cf2-b814-8c345335c6a8",  
      "onhandQuantity": {  
        "hasNumericalValue": 1,  
        "hasUnit": {  
          "id": "01FSMS8R9A8DMKVQEY5WZTF4PJ",  
          "label": "om2:one",  
          "symbol": "#"  
        }  
      },  
      "primaryAccountable": {  
        "displayUsername": "Jame4428",  
        "id": "01FSMSC4ETM84FQDWA3A21V4CC",  
        "name": "CleanLease_Service",  
        "note": null  
      },  
      "trace": [  
        {  
          "__typename": "EconomicEvent",  
          "action": {  
            "id": "produce",  
            "label": "produce"  
          },  
          "atLocation": null,  
        }  
      ]  
    }  
  }  
}
```



```
"effortQuantity": null,
"hasBeginning": null,
"hasEnd": null,
"hasPointInTime": "2022-01-17T00:00:00.000000Z",
"id": "01FSMSDKB9JSTXFN74A21N9Y6X",
"inputOf": null,
"note": "seed pool for a_tsc - 2022-01-17T00:00:00+00:00",
"outputOf": {
  "id": "01FSMSCGZR999XBAFTYZ5NPXR3",
  "name": "birth process"
},
"provider": {
  "displayUsername": "Jame4428",
  "id": "01FSMSC4ETM84FQDWA3A21V4CC",
  "name": "CleanLease_Service",
  "note": null
},
"receiver": {
  "displayUsername": "Jame4428",
  "id": "01FSMSC4ETM84FQDWA3A21V4CC",
  "name": "CleanLease_Service",
  "note": null
},
"resourceConformsTo": null,
"resourceInventoriedAs": {
  "id": "01FSMSDFVY06V41V6PWWF537A7",
  "name": "Gown"
},
"resourceQuantity": {
  "hasNumericalValue": 1,
  "hasUnit": {
    "id": "01FSMS8R9A8DMKVQEY5WZTF4PJ",
    "label": "om2:one",
    "symbol": "#"
  }
},
"toResourceInventoriedAs": null
}
],
"track": [
  {
    "__typename": "EconomicEvent",
    "action": {
      "id": "consume",
      "label": "consume"
    },
    "atLocation": null,
    "effortQuantity": null,
    "hasBeginning": null,
    "hasEnd": null,
    "hasPointInTime": "2022-01-17T00:00:00.000000Z",
    "id": "01FSMSMZ7YDDGVFORAHPFSNXXF",
    "inputOf": {
      "id": "01FSMSM366ZZH91VEG11FZAF83",
      "name": "pack process"
    },
    "note": "consume for a_tsc",
    "outputOf": null,

```



```
"provider": {
  "displayUsername": "Jame4428",
  "id": "01FSMSC4ETM84FQDWA3A21V4CC",
  "name": "CleanLease_Service",
  "note": null
},
"receiver": {
  "displayUsername": "Jame4428",
  "id": "01FSMSC4ETM84FQDWA3A21V4CC",
  "name": "CleanLease_Service",
  "note": null
},
"resourceConformsTo": null,
"resourceInventoriedAs": {
  "id": "01FSMSDFVY06V41V6PWWF537A7",
  "name": "Gown"
},
"resourceQuantity": null,
"toResourceInventoriedAs": {
  "id": "01FSMSMTOD4AWBKT66YQ46QRWY",
  "name": "Gown"
}
}
},
"trackingIdentifier": "http://cleanlease.nl/zs/53d26bce-66f8-4cf2-b814-8c345335c6a8"
}
}
```

Complete details of ReflowOS Track & Trace endpoints for use by ReflowOS client applications are listed in the Appendix section ReflowOS GraphQL Client API.

4.2 Material passport

A Material Passport is a portable cryptographic object that provides integrity, provenance and portability to an authenticated graph structure by utilizing the Reflow signature scheme, which supports unlinkable signatures of multiple parties authenticated by means of a zero-knowledge credential scheme.

The Reflow signature scheme is comprehensively defined and documented in the Reflow deliverable D2.3 REFLOW Portable Crypto Functions submitted in M24.

From page 3 of Reflow deliverable D2.3:

“Drawing on the feature of multiple signature aggregation, Reflow (signature scheme) can be used to implement a material passport for circular economy applications [Luscuere, 2017] to maintain the genealogy of a specific product, providing authenticated information about the whole set of actors, tools, collaborations, agreements, efforts and energy involved in its production, transportation and disposal [Dyne.org, 2020].

The provision of the information that forms the content of the material passport should be done by every actor in the supply chain and among the most important technical necessities for such an application are the confidentiality issues regarding access to information and the guarantees of the quality of information [Damen, 2012].”

The ReflowOS deployed infrastructure supporting the generation and validation of Material Passports consists of:

- a Hyperledger Sawtooth¹⁶ blockchain for material passport auditability over complete material flows;
- an APIRoom¹⁷ collection of Zencode scripts and API endpoints¹⁸ which generate material passports; and,
- a browser-side application which can generate or locally validate a Material Passport in QR code form.

¹⁶ <https://sawtooth.hyperledger.org/>

¹⁷ <https://dev.zenroom.org/#/pages/apiroom>

¹⁸ <https://apiroom.net/docs/ReflowDPP/>

Figure 17 illustrates the communication paths and transport protocols between a ReflowOS deployed instance and APIRoom used to validate/generate from or submit to a blockchain

APIRoom is an on-line deployment of restroom-mw¹⁹, a modular routing and transformation environment for the Zenroom²⁰ cryptographic virtual machine. APIRoom is capable of routing Zencode scripted cryptographic transformations performed by Zenroom to a variety of external systems and applications. APIRoom includes a Sawroom module which acts as a Hyperledger Sawtooth transaction processor, providing blockchain transaction processing for shared access to cryptographic signatures of immutable, accountable records of economic resource flows.

¹⁹ <https://dyne.github.io/restroom-mw/#/>

²⁰ <https://github.com/dyne/Zenroom>

4.2.1 Material passport Generation

Generation of a material passport for a specific ReflowOS material resource (a Valueflows EconomicResource data object) is performed by an APIRoom JSON REST endpoint chain²¹ with the specific EconomicResource ID given as a parameter.

The graph data for the Valueflows EconomicResource is then queried from the Reflow OS server APIRoom JSON REST API trace endpoint (see Appendix section ReflowOS APIRoom API) and the material passport signature is then generated from the cryptographic sum of all Agents, Processes and Events involved, created or consumed for it. This step is performed by APIRoom with the first Zencode script contained in the endpoint chain²²:

```
Rule caller restroom-mw
Scenario 'reflow': create Digital Product Passport

# Here we define the reflow_endpoint of the Reflow OS instance, that we are going to query
Given I have a 'string' named 'reflow_endpoint'

# here we are getting the current unix epoch and store it into 'reflow_endpoint_timestamp'
Given I have a 'string' named 'reflow_endpoint_timestamp'
Given I fetch the local timestamp and store it into 'reflow_endpoint_timestamp'

# In 'reflow_data_to_post' we write the parameters to be sent to the reflow_endpoint
# in the POST query we're about to make
# The parameters are:
# id: the id of the object you want to search in Reflow OS
# recurseLimit: how deep you want to search in the object
# unwind: this has to set to 'true' when querying Reflow OS from Restroom-mw and Apiroom
Given I have a 'string dictionary' named 'reflow_data_to_post'

# Here we do a POST query to the Reflow OS instance 'reflow_endpoint'
# passing it the content of 'reflow_data_to_post' as parameters
# The output of the query will be stored into the object 'data_from_reflow_endpoint'
# The object 'data_from_reflow_endpoint' can be a rather large JSON, if you want to print it
# just add at the end of this script the statement:
# Then print the 'data_from_reflow_endpoint'
Given I connect to 'reflow_endpoint' and pass it the content of 'reflow_data_to_post' and save the output into
'data_from_reflow_endpoint'

# Here we load the object 'data_from_reflow_endpoint'
# that we have received from the query to the Reflow OS instance
Given I have a 'string dictionary' named 'data_from_reflow_endpoint'

# Here we are telling Zenroom where the Sawroom node is
Given that I have a sawroom endpoint named 'sawroomEndpoint'
```

²¹ <https://apiroom.net/api/ReflowDPP/Reflow-create-DPP-and-store-in-sawroom.chain>

²² <https://apiroom.net/showme/zencode/ReflowDPP/Reflow-create-DPP-store-in-sawroom-1>


```
# This statement scans the 1st level of depth inside the object 'data_from_reflow_endpoint'  
# and returns an array of strings,  
# containing the values of the keys 'id', the object returned is named 'array',  
# that we are renaming to 'reflow_ids_array'  
When I create the array of elements named 'id' for dictionaries in 'data_from_reflow_endpoint'  
When I rename the 'array' to 'reflow_ids_array'  
  
# Here we do some cryptography: we create the hash-to-point of all the objects  
# contained in 'data_from_reflow_endpoint' and we sum them together  
# The result is a number, formatted as base64 by default, named 'reflow identity'  
# This is in fact the Digital Product Passport  
When I create the reflow identity of all objects in 'data_from_reflow_endpoint'  
  
# Below we're printing out the all the data we need  
# the 'reflow identity' is printed out as base58 as this encoding appears to work best with QR codes  
Then print the 'reflow_ids_array'  
Then print the 'id' from 'reflow_data_to_post'  
Then print the 'recurseLimit' from 'reflow_data_to_post'  
Then print the 'reflow_endpoint'  
Then print the 'reflow_endpoint_timestamp'  
Then print the 'reflow_identity'  
Then I ask Sawroom to store the output into the tag 'sawroom_entry'
```

Finally, the APIRoom endpoint utilises Sawroom, a Hyperledger Sawtooth blockchain transaction processor, to submit a timestamped record of the material passport to the Reflow Hyperledger Sawtooth blockchain, and returns the JSON encapsulation of material passport to the caller. This step is performed by the second Zencode script²³ in the endpoint chain with the output passed to Sawroom:

```
Scenario 'ecdh': create the signature of an object  
  
Given I have a 'string' named 'sawroom_entry'  
Given I have a 'string' named 'reflow_endpoint'  
Given I am 'https://reflow-demo.dyne.org/api/json/trace'  
Given I have my 'keyring'  
  
When I create the 'string dictionary'  
When I rename the 'string dictionary' to 'DPP'  
  
When I insert 'sawroom_entry' in 'DPP'  
When I insert 'reflow_endpoint' in 'DPP'  
  
When I create the signature of 'DPP'  
When I rename the 'signature' to 'DPP.signature'  
  
Then print the 'DPP'  
Then print the 'DPP.signature'
```

²³ <https://apiroom.net/showme/zencode/ReflowDPP/Reflow-create-DPP-store-in-sawroom-2>

Thus the Reflow material passport of an economic resource is generated and represents an authenticated, immutable and portable track record of all nodes connected in its represented graph of Valueflows elements which can be subsequently be rendered as a QR Code.

Figure 18 Illustrates an example material passport rendered as a QR Code

4.2.2 Material passport Validation

Validation of a material passport for a specific ReflowOS EconomicResource is performed by the APIRoom JSON REST API endpoint²⁴ with a specific material passport data object given as a parameter. APIRoom performs this step with a single Zencode script in the endpoint²⁵, which returns a JSON representation of the material passport stored in Sawtooth blockchain:

```
# Always use 'Rule caller restroom-mw' when using Restroom
Rule caller restroom-mw

# The scenario is not really necessary here, but nice to have
Scenario restroom: retrieve data from Sawroom

# Here we are definining the 'endpoint' to connect where Sawroom is located

Given that I have a sawroom endpoint named 'sawroomEndpoint'

# Given I have a 'string' named 'endpoint'

# The 'batch ID' is a unique indicator to retrieve data in Sawroom,
# it's returned by Sawroom when writing data
#Given I have a 'string' named 'myTag'
```

²⁴ <https://apiroom.net/api/ReflowDPP/Sawroom-Read-data-from-the-blockchain>

²⁵ <https://apiroom.net/showme/zencode/ReflowDPP/Sawroom-Read-data-from-the-blockchain>


```
# Here we are formatting the output of the reading
And I have a 'string dictionary' named 'sawroom'

# And I read the data with tag 'myTag' from sawroom and save the output into 'sawroom'

Given I read from Sawroom the data in tag 'sawroom_entry' and save the output into 'sawroom'

Then print all data
```

The graph data details for the EconomicResource can then be queried from the Reflow OS server JSON REST API trace endpoint (see Appendix section ReflowOS JSON REST API), and a Reflow signature is then generated from the dataset and compared to the signature of the material passport returned. If the signature matches, then the trace data objects returned from the ReflowOS server are identical to the data objects used to generate the material passport.

4.2.3 Material Passport Utility: reflow-dpp-pwa

The progressive web application, reflow-dpp-pwa²⁶ can be run in browsers on laptops or phones or installed as a web application on mobile devices to demonstrate the generation and validation material passports.

To generate a new material passport, a Valueflows EconomicResource ID is entered. The application submits the ID to the APIRoom endpoint server and renders the results as a QR code.

²⁶ <https://reflow-dpp.netlify.app/>

Figure 19 shows Material Passport generation and QR code rendering via the reflow-dpp-pwa application

To validate a material passport, the application scans a material passport QR code and independently validates it locally using the Javascript Zenroom implementation loaded on the local device by the application. As a secondary security measure, it also validates the material passport against the ReflowOS Hyperledger Sawtooth blockchain entry returned by APIRoom.

Figure 20 illustrates three screenshots of reflow-dpp-pwa material passport validation and associated JSON data object detailed expansion

Note that the application references a material passport as a “digital product passport” or DPP in alignment with recent European Commission pre-normative standard nomenclature for such cryptographic data objects.

The repository for reflow-dpp-pwa source code is available at <https://github.com/dyne/reflow-dpp-pwa>.

5. Multi-Platform installation & component deployment

5.1 ReflowOS server cloud VM deployment

Deployment of a ReflowOS server and its default Phoenix client application on a cloud virtual machine is possible through the ReflowOS installer github repository²⁷, which can install a ReflowOS server instance together with its integrated GraphQL client, GraphiQL, which is useful for initial testing and diagnosis.

5.1.1 Cloud Pre-Installation Requirements

The ReflowOS installer requires a cloud-provisioned Linux based target host that has:

²⁷ <https://github.com/dyne/reflow-os>

- a minimum of 2Gb RAM;
- a minimum of 10Gb free storage;
- a running Docker daemon;
- a public network interface reachable by a globally routable IP address;
- a fully qualified domain name (FQDN) assigned to the publicly reachable network interface address (required for federation)
- a TLS certificate issued and for the FQDN and configured on a reverse proxy or use and configure the included Caddy container with a Let's Encrypt certificate (required for federation)

5.1.2 Cloud Installation & Configuration

At the virtual console or remotely via ssh, install the ReflowOS server as follows

```
# clone the repo
git clone https://github.com/dyne/reflow-os

# enter local workspace
cd reflow-os

# configure the FQDN HOSTNAME as well as SERVER_PORT and PUBLIC_PORT in
configuration file conf/bonfire-public.env

FLAVOUR=reflow
# COPY this file to /config/{dev|prod}/public.env and change any values as required
# server domain name:
HOSTNAME=localhost
# server port:
SERVER_PORT=4000
# port your visitors will access (typically 80 or 443, will be different than SERVER_PORT only if
using a reve
rse proxy)
PUBLIC_PORT=4000
# hostname and port of meili search index
SEARCH_MEILI_INSTANCE=http://localhost:7700
# require an email address to be invited before being able to sign up
INVITE_ONLY=false

# configure for smtp auth
MAIL_BACKEND=smtp
MAIL_DOMAIN=smtp.sendgrid.net
MAIL_PORT=587

# a name and tagline for your instance
INSTANCE_DESCRIPTION="Reflow node for valueflows circular economy networks"
# uncomment in order to NOT automatically change the database schema when you upgrade the app
```



```
# DISABLE_DB_AUTOMIGRATION=true
# max file upload size (default is 20 meg)
UPLOAD_LIMIT=30000000
# =====
# You should not have to edit any of the following ones:
APP_NAME=reflow
POSTGRES_HOST=localhost
LANG=en_US.UTF-8
REPLACE_OS_VARS=true
LIVEVIEW_ENABLED=true

ACME_AGREE=true

# activate configuration and compose and install docker containers
make config setup

# run the reflowos server with console to test
make run

# or to run the reflowos server in the background
make bg
```

Within the constraints of the pre-installation requirements, this deployment method can also be used to deploy on-premises ReflowOS server instances.

For up to date installation and configuration instructions for the latest release of the reflow-os docker containers, consult the on-line installation instructions at <https://github.com/dyne/reflow-os>

5.1.3 Cloud scaling practices

There are several methods to consider when planning to cater for increased capacity in a cloud VM deployed ReflowOS server instance.

The traditional intermediate approach is to split the ReflowOS instance services running on a single VM server into a classic load balanced 2 tiered service, utilising the cloud providers' virtual networking and load balancing facilities to balance load capacities of the web servers, and utilise standard clustering techniques for the databases and filestores. This approach is best suited for a large to very large scale deployment of a single ReflowOS instance.

A better staged incremental approach, more in line with the ReflowOS federation model, is to split the fully qualified domain name of an existing ReflowOS instance into multiple subdomains and run multiple ReflowOS server instances, one for each subdomain of the FQDN. This approach requires deployment and capacity planning based on organisational structure or regional based staged service roll-out, but allows for greater

flexibility for hybrid deployments across multiple cloud providers as well as independent on-premises deployments when needed.

5.1.4 Continuous Integration Tool

A continuous integration and deployment (CI/CD) tool, terrafloWS, has been developed to facilitate community development and deployment management. The tool also allows for cloud scaling management by utilising standard devops deployment and configuration tools. Automation of cloud deployment, installation and configuration of multiple ReflowOS instances is achieved, as terrafloWS is built on terraform²⁸ for flexible deployment on hybrid cloud infrastructures (including AWS, Google Cloud Platform and private clouds), and utilises ansible²⁹ playbooks for idempotent installation and configuration management of each cloud instance.

To install terrafloWS:

```
git clone https://github.com/reflow-project/terrafloWS
cd terrafloWS/reflowOS
```

After taking note of the pre-installation dependencies and installing and configuring required particular terraform cloud or virtual machine provider(s) the following commands will raise ReflowOS server instances into the configured deployment environments.

```
make init # one shot initialization of terraform
make apply # raise ReflowOS server instances
make play # apply ansible playbooks to each server instance
```

For up to date documentation, refer to the terrafloWS code repository found at <https://github.com/reflow-project/terrafloWS>.

5.2 Embedded ReflowOS component deployment

5.2.1 ReflowOS server deployment on embedded hardware

Instead of utilising Docker containers which are more useful for cloud environments, the ReflowOS server can also be built natively on Linux supported single-board computer (SBC) platforms based on alternative machine hardware architectures such as ARM64.

The direct SBC (non-Docker based) ReflowOS build and install requires a Linux-based SBC host that has:

²⁸ <https://www.terraform.io/>

²⁹ <https://www.ansible.com/>

- a minimum of 2Gb RAM;
- a minimum of 5Gb free storage;
- a running Postgres (or postgres) daemon;
- a public network interface reachable by a globally routable IP address;
- a fully qualified domain name (FQDN) assigned to the publicly reachable network interface address (required for federation)
- a reverse web proxy configured for HTTPS on TCP port 443 serving a TLS certificate issued and for the FQDN assigned (required for federation)
- all build package dependencies installed, including postgres, build-tools, erlang and elixir

The ReflowOS server can be natively built for embedded SBC hardware platforms such as the ARM64 based Raspberry Pi using via the build documentation of the bonfire-app git repository, specifically with build variables set to:

```
FLAVOUR=reflow
WITH_DOCKER=no

# clone repository and enter workspace
git clone https://github.com/dyne/bonfire_app
cd bonfire_app
FLAVOUR=reflow WITH_DOCKER=no ORG_NAME=dyne MIX_ENV=prod make -C bonfire pre.config
# make passwords and secrets
make secrets
```

The output of the final commands will give the path of configuration files to edit before continuing (see the Cloud Installation and Configuration section for configuration file details).

```
# downloads and builds elixir and javascript dependencies
FLAVOUR=reflow WITH_DOCKER=no ORG_NAME=dyne MIX_ENV=prod make -C bonfire setup
```

Finally, to run the ReflowOS server

```
# run the reflowos server with console (run within tmux or screen for deployment)
make dev
```

For up to date build dependencies, configuration, build and deployment instructions for the latest build release of the ReflowOS server, refer to the on-line installation instructions contained within the bonfire_app repository https://github.com/dyne/bonfire_app.

5.2.2 ReflowOS client applications on embedded & IoT hardware

Embedded ReflowOS client applications can be developed for most embedded hardware environments capable of communicating over HTTPS.

Arduino is an open-source electronic project and includes an embedded development IDE platform that supports a large and ever growing ecosystem of various embedded hardware environments.

For example, the Arduino IDE platform is utilized by the Milan pilot BOTTO hardware device developed and used within the Milan Foody Zero waste use case. The heart of the custom built BOTTO device is an embedded ESP32 SoC (System on a Chip). The BOTTO firmware sends GraphQL queries to the ReflowOS GraphQL API of a ReflowOS server to search and create Valueflows offers and intents.

The open-source firmware for the ESP32 based ReflowOS client application can be found in the Milan-pilot repository <https://github.com/reflow-project/Milan-pilot>.

See section 5.4.2 of REFLOW deliverable 5.4 Reflow Pilot Applications for comprehensive details of the BOTTO and the Milan pilot Foody Zero Waste use case.

5.2.3 ReflowOS client application environments interacting with embedded hardware

Node-RED³⁰ is a modular graphical flow-based programming and application environment based on nodejs that can be used to interface and control a wide variety of embedded protocols and devices.

With its existing GraphQL client modules, an example Node-RED flow simulation tool acting as a ReFlowOS client application was developed by Milan and Amsterdam pilots. It can easily be further extended to interface with Node-RED's extensive compatibility library for IoT sensor and actuator modules (for a huge variety of industrial and other hardware interfaces) to detect and enact EconomicEvents upon EconomicResources.

The source code repository for the Node-RED ReflowOS client application developed by Milan and Amsterdam pilot partners can be found at <https://github.com/reflow-project/Node-red>.

See section 4.3 of REFLOW deliverable 5.4 Reflow Pilot Applications for further details of Amsterdam & Milan pilot use of Node-RED.

5.2.4 Future Multi-Platform ReflowOS Zenroom applications

Zenroom offers a multi-platform environment to support the development of further applications for ReflowOS client applications, particularly for future innovative developments utilizing Material Passports. Zenroom binaries and library platform availability include:

- Linux based X86_64 executable and libraries
- Linux native ARMHF executable and libraries
- Linux ARM64 executable and libraries

³⁰ <https://nodered.org/>

- Android native libraries (ARM, ARM64)
- iOS native libraries
- Javascript packages for nodejs, React and in-browser execution

For example, the progressive web application `reflow-dpp-pwa` utilizes the Zenroom Javascript package to validate material passports on the device cryptographically. This allows for portable autonomous on-device trust verification even independently of access to blockchain queries. With no dependencies and a lightweight memory footprint, Zenroom supports future development of multi-platform embedded and semi-embedded ReflowOS components, from embedded systems-on-chips (SoCs) & single-board computers (SBCs) to mobile platforms (iOS & Android) to Linux-based automotive and IoT controllers.

See the Zenroom downloads³¹ web page for an up to date list of available Zenroom binary images, supporting libraries, as well as bindings for a variety of programming language environments, including Rust and Go.

6. Conclusions

The minimalist modular approach to the design and implementation of ReflowOS architecture and components enable the flexible bridging of data center and cloud-based service components together with on-premises hosted and embedded components.

³¹ <https://zenroom.org/#downloads>

Figure 21 Illustrates a hybrid cloud and embedded deployment of ReflowOS components

The bridging of ReflowOS components out from the non-local data center clouds into local embedded deployment scenarios facilitates a more fine grained local measurement and actuation development of circular activity whilst offering deployment options that keep data flows and storage close to the local and regional participants and resources.

Through its tools, ReflowOS can offer detailed data insights and evidence-based feedback for use in assessment of levers beyond the Product and Tech Innovation layer of the Reflow Framework to facilitate the journey of continuous improvement of circular economic development.

Through its component platform deployment options, ReflowOS offers macro scaling capacities in the cloud for inter and intra organisational participation growth, as well as micro scaling capacity at the embedded device layer for increased dimensionality and resolution of locally sensed measurement observations and actuated events, offering higher fidelity continuous assessment of network and urban metabolisms.

7. Appendix: APIs & Data Object References

7.1 ReflowOS APIs

7.1.1 ReflowOS GraphQL Client API Schema

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Query (RootQueryType)

Field	Argument	Type	Description
action		Action	
	id	ID	
actions		[Action !]	
activity		Activity	Get an activity
	filter	ActivityFilters	
agent		Agent	Find an agent (person or organization) by their ID
	id	ID	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
agentRelationship		AgentRelationship	Retrieve details of an agent relationship by its ID
	id	ID	
agentRelationshipRole		AgentRelationshipRole	Retrieve details of an agent relationship role by its ID
	id	ID	
agentRelationshipRoles		[AgentRelationshipRole!]	Retrieve all possible kinds of associations that agents may have with one another in this collaboration space
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
agentRelationships		[AgentRelationship!]	Retrieve details of all the relationships between all agents registered in this collaboration space
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
agents		[Agent!]	Loads all agents publicly registered within this collaboration space
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
agreement		Agreement	
	id	ID	
agreements		[Agreement!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
categories		CategoriesPage!	Get list of categories we know about
	after	[Cursor!]	
	before	[Cursor!]	
	limit	Int	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
category		Category	Get a category by ID
	categoryId	ID	
claim		Claim	
	id	ID	
claims		[Claim!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
commitment		Commitment	
	id	ID	
commitments		[Commitment!]	
	filter	agentCommitmentSearchParams	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
economicEvent		EconomicEvent	
	id	ID	
economicEvents		[EconomicEvent!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
economicEventsFiltered		[EconomicEvent!]	
	action	ID	
	endDate	String	
	providerId	ID	
	receiverId	ID	
	resourceClassifiedAs	[URI!]	
	startDate	String	
economicEventsPages		EconomicEventPage!	Get paginated list of economic events
	after	[Cursor!]	
	before	[Cursor!]	
	limit	Int	
economicResource		EconomicResource	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
	id	ID	
economicResources		[EconomicResource!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
economicResourcesFiltered		[EconomicResource]	TEMPORARY - get filtered but non-paginated list of resources
	agent	[ID]	
	currentLocation	[ID]	
	geolocation	GeolocationFilters	
	inScopeOf	[ID]	
	state	[ID]	
	tagIds	[ID]	
	trackingIdentifier	[String]	
economicResourcesPages		EconomicResourcePage!	Get paginated list of economic resources
	after	[Cursor!]	
	before	[Cursor!]	
	limit	Int	
feed		[Activity]	Get activities in a feed
	filter	FeedFilters	
	paginate	Paginate	
fulfillment		Fulfillment	
	id	ID	
fulfillments		[Fulfillment!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
intent		Intent	
	id	ID	
intents		[Intent!]	
	filter	IntentSearchParams	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
intentsPages		IntentsPage!	Get paginated list of intents
	after	[Cursor!]	
	before	[Cursor!]	
	limit	Int	
me		Me	Get information about and for the current user
measure		Measure	
	id	ID	
measures		[Measure!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
measuresPages		MeasuresPage!	
	after	[Cursor]	
	before	[Cursor]	
	limit	Int	
myAgent		Agent	Loads details of the currently authenticated REA agent
needsPages		IntentsPage!	Get paginated list of active needs (intents with no provider)
	after	[Cursor!]	
	before	[Cursor!]	
	limit	Int	
observablePhenomenon		ObservablePhenomenon	
	id	ID	
observablePhenomenonPages		ObservablePhenomenonPage!	Get paginated list of observable phenomenon
	after	[Cursor!]	
	before	[Cursor!]	
	limit	Int	
observablePhenomenons		[ObservablePhenomenon!]	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
observableProperties		[ObservableProperty!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
observablePropertiesPages		ObservablePropertyPage!	Get paginated list of observable properties
	after	[Cursor!]	
	before	[Cursor!]	
	limit	Int	
observableProperty		ObservableProperty	
	id	ID	
observation		Observation	
	id	ID	
observations		[Observation!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
observationsPages		ObservationPage!	Get paginated list of observations
	after	[Cursor!]	
	agent	[ID!]	
	before	[Cursor!]	
	hasFeatureOfInterest	[ID!]	
	limit	Int	
	madeBySensor	[ID!]	
	observedDuring	[ID!]	
	observedProperty	[ID!]	
	provider	[ID!]	
offersPages		IntentsPage!	Get paginated list of active offers (intents with no receiver)
	after	[Cursor!]	
	before	[Cursor!]	
	limit	Int	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
organization		Organization	Find an organization (group) agent by its ID
	id	ID	
organizations		[Organization!]	Loads all organizations publicly registered within this collaboration space
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
organizationsPages		AgentsPage!	Get paginated list of organizations
	after	[Cursor!]	
	before	[Cursor!]	
	limit	Int	
people		[Person!]	Loads all people who have publicly registered with this collaboration space.
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
peoplePages		AgentsPage!	Get paginated list of people
	after	[Cursor!]	
	before	[Cursor!]	
	limit	Int	
person		Person	Find a person by their ID
	id	ID	
plan		Plan	
	id	ID	
plans		[Plan!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
post		Post	Get a post

Field	Argument	Type	Description
	filter	PostFilters	
posts		[Post]	Get all posts
process		Process	
	id	ID	
processSpecification		ProcessSpecification	
	id	ID	
processSpecifications		[ProcessSpecification!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
processes		[Process!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
processesPages		ProcessPage!	Get paginated list of processes
	after	[Cursor!]	
	before	[Cursor!]	
	limit	Int	
productBatch		ProductBatch	
	id	ID	
productBatches		[ProductBatch!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
proposal		Proposal	
	id	ID	
proposals		[Proposal!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
proposalsFiltered		[Proposal]	TEMPORARY - get filtered but non-paginated list of proposals
	agent	[ID]	
	atLocation	[ID]	
	geolocation	GeolocationFilters	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
	inScopeOf	[ID]	
proposalsPages		ProposalsPage!	Get paginated list of proposals
	after	[Cursor!]	
	before	[Cursor!]	
	limit	Int	
recipeExchange		RecipeExchange	
	id	ID	
recipeExchanges		[RecipeExchange!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
recipeFlow		RecipeFlow	
	id	ID	
recipeFlows		[RecipeFlow!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
recipeProcess		RecipeProcess	
	id	ID	
recipeProcesses		[RecipeProcess!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
recipeResource		RecipeResource	
	id	ID	
recipeResources		[RecipeResource!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
resourceSpecification		ResourceSpecification	
	id	ID	
resourceSpecifications		[ResourceSpecification!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
resourceSpecificationsPages		ResourceSpecificationPage!	Get paginated list of resource specifications

Field	Argument	Type	Description
	after	[Cursor!]	
	before	[Cursor!]	
	inScopeOf	[ID]	
	limit	Int	
	tagIds	[ID]	
satisfaction		Satisfaction	
	id	ID	
satisfactions		[Satisfaction!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
scenario		Scenario	
	id	ID	
scenarioDefinition		ScenarioDefinition	
	id	ID	
scenarioDefinitions		[ScenarioDefinition!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
scenarios		[Scenario!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
settlement		Settlement	
	id	ID	
settlements		[Settlement!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
spatialThing		SpatialThing	
	id	ID	
spatialThings		[SpatialThing!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
spatialThingsPages		SpatialThingsPage!	
	after	[Cursor]	
	before	[Cursor]	
	limit	Int	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
tag		Tag	Get a tag by ID
	id	ID	
unit		Unit	
	id	ID	
units		[Unit!]	
	limit	Int	
	start	ID	
unitsPages		UnitsPage!	
	after	[Cursor]	
	before	[Cursor]	
	limit	Int	
user		User	Get a user
	filter	CharacterFilters	
valueCalculation		ValueCalculation	
	id	ID	
valueCalculationsPages		ValueCalculationPage!	
	after	[Cursor!]	
	before	[Cursor!]	
	limit	Int	

Mutation (RootMutationType)

Field	Argument	Type	Description
addTeamMember		String	Share the current user identity with a team member. This will give them full access to the currently authenticated user identity. Warning: anyone you add will have admin-level access over this user identity, meaning they can post as this user, read private messages, etc.
	label	String!	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
			Organisation, Team, etc)
	usernameOrEmail	String!	Who to add (they need to be an existing user on this instance)
boost		Activity	
	id	String!	
changePassword		Me	Change account password
	oldPassword	String!	
	password	String!	
	passwordConfirmation	String!	
confirmEmail		Me	Confirm email address using a token generated upon signup or with request_confirm_email and emailed to the user.
	token	String!	
createAgentRelationship		AgentRelationshipResponse	
	relationship	AgentRelationshipCreateParams!	
createAgentRelationshipRole		AgentRelationshipRoleResponse	
	agentRelationshipRole	AgentRelationshipRoleCreateParams	
createAgreement		AgreementResponse	
	agreement	AgreementCreateParams	
createAppreciation		AppreciationResponse	
	appreciation	AppreciationCreateParams!	
createCategory		Category	Create a new Category
	category	CategoryInput	
createClaim		ClaimResponse	
	claim	ClaimCreateParams!	
createCommitment		CommitmentResponse	
	commitment	CommitmentCreateParams	
createEconomicEvent		EconomicEventResponse	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
	event	EconomicEventCreateParams!	
	newInventoriedResource	EconomicResourceCreateParams	
createFulfillment		FulfillmentResponse	
	fulfillment	FulfillmentCreateParams!	
createIntent		IntentResponse	
	intent	IntentCreateParams	
createNeed		IntentResponse	Creates a new need for the logged in user, will ignore any receiver specified.
	intent	IntentCreateParams	
createObservablePhenomenon		ObservablePhenomenon	
	observablePhenomenon	ObservablePhenomenonInputParams!	
createObservableProperty		ObservableProperty	
	observableProperty	ObservablePropertyInputParams!	
createObservation		Observation!	
	observation	ObservationInputParams!	
createOffer		IntentResponse	Creates a new offer for the logged in user, will ignore any provider specified.
	intent	IntentCreateParams	
createOrganization		OrganizationResponse	Registers a new organization (group agent) with the collaboration space
	organization	AgentCreateParams!	
createPerson		PersonResponse	Registers a new (human) person with the collaboration space
	person	AgentCreateParams!	
createPlan		PlanResponse	
	plan	PlanCreateParams!	
createPost		Post	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
	postContent	PostContentInput!	
	replyTo	ID	
	toCircles	[ID]	
createProcess		ProcessResponse	
	process	ProcessCreateParams!	
createProcessSpecification		ProcessSpecificationResponse	
	processSpecification	ProcessSpecificationCreateParams	
createProductBatch		ProductBatchResponse	
	productBatch	ProductBatchCreateParams!	
createProposal		ProposalResponse	
	proposal	ProposalCreateParams	
createRecipeExchange		RecipeExchangeResponse	
	recipeExchange	RecipeExchangeCreateParams	
createRecipeFlow		RecipeFlowResponse	
	recipeFlow	RecipeFlowCreateParams	
createRecipeProcess		RecipeProcessResponse	
	recipeProcess	RecipeProcessCreateParams	
createRecipeResource		RecipeResourceResponse	
	recipeResource	RecipeResourceCreateParams	
createResourceSpecification		ResourceSpecificationResponse	
	resourceSpecification	ResourceSpecificationCreateParams	
createSatisfaction		SatisfactionResponse	
	satisfaction	SatisfactionCreateParams	
createScenario		ScenarioResponse	
	plan	ScenarioCreateParams!	
createScenarioDefinition		ScenarioDefinitionResponse	
	plan	ScenarioDefinitionCreateParams!	
createSettlement		SettlementResponse	
	settlement	SettlementCreateParams!	
createSpatialThing		SpatialThingResponse	
	inScopeOf	ID	
	spatialThing	SpatialThingCreateParams!	
createUnit		UnitResponse	
	unit	UnitCreateParams!	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
createUser		Me	Request a new user identity for the authenticated account
	character	CharacterInput!	
	profile	ProfileInput!	
createValueCalculation		ValueCalculationResponse	
	valueCalculation	ValueCalculationCreateParams!	
delete		AnyContext	Delete more or less anything
	contextId	String!	
deleteAgentRelationship		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteAgentRelationshipRole		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteAgreement		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteAppreciation		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteClaim		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteCommitment		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteEconomicEvent		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteEconomicResource		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteFulfillment		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteIntent		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteObservablePhenomenon		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteObservableProperty		Boolean	
	id	ID!	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
deleteObservation		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteOrganization		Boolean	Erase record of an organization and thus remove it from the collaboration space
	id	ID!	
deletePerson		Boolean	Erase record of a person and thus remove them from the collaboration space
	id	ID!	
deletePlan		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteProcess		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteProcessSpecification		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteProductBatch		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteProposal		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteProposedIntent		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteProposedTo		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteRecipeExchange		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteRecipeFlow		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteRecipeProcess		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteRecipeResource		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteResourceSpecification		Boolean	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
	id	ID!	
deleteSatisfaction		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteScenario		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteScenarioDefinition		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteSettlement		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteSpatialThing		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteUnit		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
deleteValueCalculation		Boolean	
	id	ID!	
flag		Activity	
	id	String!	
follow		Activity	
	id	String!	
	username	String!	
like		Activity	
	id	String!	
login		LoginResponse	Authenticate an account and/or user
	emailOrUsername	String!	
	password	String!	
makeTag		Tag	Create a Tag out of something else. You can also directly use the tag() mutation with a pointer ID instead.
	contextId	String	
proposeIntent		ProposedIntentResponse	Include an existing intent as part of a proposal. @param

Field	Argument	Type	Description
			publishedIn the (Proposal) to include the intent in @param publishes the (Intent) to include as part of the proposal
	publishedIn	ID!	
	publishes	ID!	
	reciprocal	Boolean	
proposeTo		ProposedToResponse	Send a proposal to another agent. @param proposed the (Proposal) to send to an involved agent @param proposedTo the (Agent) to include in the proposal
	proposed	ID!	
	proposedTo	ID!	
requestConfirmEmail		String	Request a new confirmation email
	email	String!	
requestResetPassword		String	Request an email to be sent to reset a forgotten password
	email	String!	
selectUser		LoginResponse	Switch to a user (among those from the authenticated account)
	username	String!	
signup		String	Register a new account. Returns the created account_id
	email	String!	
	inviteCode	String	
	password	String!	
tag		Boolean	Tag a thing (using a Pointer) with one or more Tags (or

Field	Argument	Type	Description
			Categories, or even Pointers to anything that can become tag)
	tags	[String]!	
	thing	String!	
updateAgentRelationship		AgentRelationshipResponse	
	relationship	AgentRelationshipUpdateParams!	
updateAgentRelationshipRole		AgentRelationshipRoleResponse	
	agentRelationshipRole	AgentRelationshipRoleUpdateParams	
updateAgreement		AgreementResponse	
	agreement	AgreementUpdateParams	
updateAppreciation		AppreciationResponse	
	appreciation	AppreciationUpdateParams!	
updateCategory		Category	Update a category
	category	CategoryInput	
	categoryId	ID	
updateClaim		ClaimResponse	
	claim	ClaimUpdateParams!	
updateCommitment		CommitmentResponse	
	commitment	CommitmentUpdateParams	
updateEconomicEvent		EconomicEventResponse	
	event	EconomicEventUpdateParams!	
updateEconomicResource		EconomicResourceResponse	
	resource	EconomicResourceUpdateParams!	
updateFulfillment		FulfillmentResponse	
	fulfillment	FulfillmentUpdateParams!	
updateIntent		IntentResponse	
	intent	IntentUpdateParams	
updateObservablePhenomenon		ObservablePhenomenon	
	observablePhenomenon	ObservablePhenomenonInputParams!	
updateObservableProperty		ObservableProperty	
	observableProperty	ObservablePropertyInputParams!	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
updateObservation		Observation!	
	observation	ObservationInputParams!	
updateOrganization		OrganizationResponse	Update organization profile details
	organization	AgentUpdateParams!	
updatePerson		PersonResponse	Update profile details
	person	AgentUpdateParams!	
updatePlan		PlanResponse	
	plan	PlanUpdateParams!	
updateProcess		ProcessResponse	
	process	ProcessUpdateParams!	
updateProcessSpecification		ProcessSpecificationResponse	
	processSpecification	ProcessSpecificationUpdateParams	
updateProductBatch		ProductBatchResponse	
	productBatch	ProductBatchUpdateParams!	
updateProposal		ProposalResponse	
	proposal	ProposalUpdateParams	
updateRecipeExchange		RecipeExchangeResponse	
	recipeExchange	RecipeExchangeUpdateParams	
updateRecipeFlow		RecipeFlowResponse	
	recipeFlow	RecipeFlowUpdateParams	
updateRecipeProcess		RecipeProcessResponse	
	recipeProcess	RecipeProcessUpdateParams	
updateRecipeResource		RecipeResourceResponse	
	recipeResource	RecipeResourceUpdateParams	
updateResourceSpecification		ResourceSpecificationResponse	
	resourceSpecification	ResourceSpecificationUpdateParams	
updateSatisfaction		SatisfactionResponse	
	satisfaction	SatisfactionUpdateParams	
updateScenario		ScenarioResponse	
	plan	ScenarioUpdateParams!	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
updateScenarioDefinition		ScenarioDefinitionResponse	
	plan	ScenarioDefinitionUpdateParams!	
updateSettlement		SettlementResponse	
	s0ettlement	SettlementUpdateParams!	
updateSpatialThing		SpatialThingResponse	
	spatialThing	SpatialThingUpdateParams!	
updateUnit		UnitResponse	
	unit	UnitUpdateParams!	
updateUser		Me	Edit user profile
	profile	ProfileInput!	
updateValueCalculation		ValueCalculationResponse	
	valueCalculation	ValueCalculationUpdateParams!	

Objects

Action

An action verb defining the kind of event, commitment, or intent. It is recommended that the lowercase action verb should be used as the record ID in order that references to Actions elsewhere in the system are easily readable.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
id		ID!	
inputOutput		String	Denotes if a process input or output, or not related to a process.
label		String!	A unique verb which defines the action.
note		String	
onhandEffect		String	The onhand effect of an economic event on a resource, increment, decrement, no effect, or decrement resource and increment 'to' resource.
pairsWith		String	The action that should be included on the other direction of the process, for example accept with modify.
resourceEffect		String!	The accounting effect of an economic event on a resource, increment, decrement, no effect, or decrement resource and increment 'to' resource.

Activity

Field	Argument	Type	Description
directReplies		[Replied]	
	paginate	Paginate	
id		ID	
object		AnyContext	
objectId		String	
subject		AnyCharacter	
subjectId		String	
verb		Verb	

AgentRelationship

The role of an economic relationship that exists between 2 agents, such as member, trading partner.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
id		ID!	
inScopeOf		[AccountingScope!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
note		String	A textual description or comment.
object		Agent!	The object of a relationship between 2 agents. For example, if Mary is a member of a group, then the group is the object.
relationship		AgentRelationshipRole!	A kind of relationship that exists between 2 agents.
subject		Agent!	The subject of a relationship between 2 agents. For example, if Mary is a member of a group, then Mary is the subject.

AgentRelationshipResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
agentRelationship		AgentRelationship!	

AgentRelationshipRole

A relationship role defining the kind of association one agent can have with another.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
id		ID!	
inverseRoleLabel		String	The human readable name of the role, from the object to the

Field	Argument	Type	Description
			subject.
note		String	A textual description or comment.
roleLabel		String!	The human readable name of the role, from the subject to the object.

AgentRelationshipRoleResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
agentRelationshipRole		AgentRelationshipRole	

AgentsPage

A page of agents

Field	Argument	Type	Description
edges		[Agent!]!	
pageInfo		PageInfo!	
totalCount		Int!	

Agreement

Any type of agreement among economic agents.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
commitments		[Commitment!]	
created		DateTime	The date and time the agreement was created.
economicEvents		[EconomicEvent!]	
id		ID!	
involvedAgents		[Agent!]	
name		String	An informal or formal textual identifier for an agreement. Does not imply uniqueness.
note		String	A textual description or comment.

AgreementResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
agreement		Agreement	

Appreciation

A way to tie an economic event that is given in loose fulfilment for another economic event, without commitments or expectations. Supports the gift economy.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
appreciationOf		EconomicEvent!	The economic event this appreciation has been given in acknowledgement of.
appreciationWith		EconomicEvent!	The economic event provided as a gift in this appreciation.
id		ID!	
note		String	A textual description or comment.

AppreciationResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
appreciation		Appreciation	

CategoriesPage

Field	Argument	Type	Description
edges		[Category!]!	
pageInfo		PageInfo!	
totalCount		Int!	

Category

A category (eg. tag in a taxonomy)

Field	Argument	Type	Description
caretaker		AnyContext	The caretaker of this category, if any
extraInfo		Json	A JSON document containing more info beyond the default fields
facet		String	
id		ID	The numeric primary key of the category
name		String	
parentCategory		Category	The parent category (in a tree-based taxonomy)

Field	Argument	Type	Description
parentCategoryId		String	
prefix		String	
subCategories		[CategoriesPage]	List of child categories (in a tree-based taxonomy)
summary		String	

Character

Field	Argument	Type	Description
username		String	

Claim

A claim for a future economic event(s) in reciprocity for an economic event that already occurred. For example, a claim for payment for goods received.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
action		Action!	Relates a claim to a verb, such as consume, produce, work, improve, etc.
agreedIn		URI	Reference to an agreement between agents which specifies the rules or policies or calculations which govern this claim.
calculatedUsing		ValueCalculation	Specifies if a calculation will be applied to this claim when an economic event is logged.
created		DateTime	The data on which the claim was made.
due		DateTime	The time the claim is expected to be settled.
effortQuantity		Measure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be cycle counts or other measures of effort or usefulness.
finished		Boolean	The claim is complete or not. This is irrespective of if the original goal has been met, and indicates that no

Field	Argument	Type	Description
			more will be done.
id		ID!	
inScopeOf		[AccountingScope!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
note		String	A textual description or comment.
provider		Agent!	The economic agent from whom the claim is initiated.
receiver		Agent!	The economic agent whom the claim is for.
resourceClassifiedAs		[URI!]	References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
resourceConformsTo		ResourceSpecification	The primary resource specification or definition of an existing or potential economic resource. A resource will have only one, as this specifies exactly what the resource is.
resourceQuantity		Measure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried.
triggeredBy		EconomicEvent!	The economic event which already occurred which this claim has been made against.

ClaimResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
claim		Claim	

Commitment

A planned economic flow that has been promised by an agent to another agent.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
action		Action!	Relates a commitment to a verb, such as consume,

Field	Argument	Type	Description
			produce, work, improve, etc.
agreedIn		URI	Reference to an agreement between agents which specifies the rules or policies or calculations which govern this commitment.
atLocation		SpatialThing	The place where a commitment occurs. Usually mappable.
clauseOf		Agreement	This commitment is part of the exchange agreement.
created		DateTime	The creation time of the commitment.
deletable		Boolean	The commitment can be safely deleted, has no dependent information.
due		DateTime	The time something is expected to be complete.
effortQuantity		Measure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be cycle counts or other measures of effort or usefulness.
finished		Boolean	The commitment is complete or not. This is irrespective of if the original goal has been met, and indicates that no more will be done.
fulfilledBy		[Fulfillment!]	The economic event which completely or partially fulfills a commitment.
hasBeginning		DateTime	The planned beginning of the commitment.
hasEnd		DateTime	The planned end of the commitment.
hasPointInTime		DateTime	The planned date/time for the commitment. Can be used instead of beginning and end.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
id		ID!	
inScopeOf		[AccountingScope!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
independentDemandOf		Plan	Represents a desired deliverable expected from this plan.
inputOf		Process	Defines the process to which this commitment is an input.
involvedAgents		[Agent!]	
note		String	A textual description or comment.
outputOf		Process	Defines the process for which this commitment is an output.
provider		Agent!	The economic agent from whom the commitment is initiated.
receiver		Agent!	The economic agent whom the commitment is for.
resourceClassifiedAs		[URI!]	References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
resourceConformsTo		ResourceSpecification	The primary resource specification or definition of an existing or potential economic resource. A resource will have only one, as this specifies exactly what the resource is.
resourceInventoriedAs		EconomicResource	Exact economic resource involved in the commitment.
resourceQuantity		Measure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried.
satisfies		[Satisfaction!]	An intent satisfied fully or partially by an

Field	Argument	Type	Description
			economic event or commitment.

CommitmentResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
commitment		Commitment	

Duration

A Duration represents an interval between two DateTime values.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
numericDuration		Float!	A number representing the duration, will be paired with a unit.
unitType		TimeUnit!	A unit of measure.

EconomicEvent

An observed economic flow, as opposed to a flow planned to happen in the future. This could reflect a change in the quantity of an economic resource. It is also defined by its behavior in relation to the economic resource (see Action)

Field	Argument	Type	Description
action		Action!	Relates an economic event to a verb, such as consume, produce, work, improve, etc.
agreedIn		URI	Reference to an agreement between agents which specifies the rules or policies or calculations which govern this economic event.
appreciatedBy		[Appreciation!]	
appreciationOf		[Appreciation!]	
atLocation		SpatialThing	The place where an economic event occurs. Usually mappable.
calculatedUsing		ValueCalculation	The value calculation (if any) used to generate this

Field	Argument	Type	Description
			event.
deletable		Boolean	The economic event can be safely deleted, has no dependent information.
effortQuantity		Measure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be cycle counts or other measures of effort or usefulness.
fulfills		[Fulfillment!]	The commitment which is completely or partially fulfilled by an economic event.
hasBeginning		DateTime	The beginning of the economic event.
hasEnd		DateTime	The end of the economic event.
hasPointInTime		DateTime	The date/time at which the economic event occurred. Can be used instead of beginning and end.
id		ID!	
inScopeOf		[AccountingScope!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
inputOf		Process	Defines the process to which this event is an input.
note		String	A textual description or comment.
outputOf		Process	Defines the process for which this event is an output.
provider		Agent!	The economic agent from whom the actual economic event is initiated.
realizationOf		Agreement	This economic event occurs as part of this agreement.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
receiver		Agent!	The economic agent whom the actual economic event is for.
resourceClassifiedAs		[URI!]	References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
resourceConformsTo		ResourceSpecification	The primary resource specification or definition of an existing or potential economic resource. A resource will have only one, as this specifies exactly what the resource is.
resourceInventoriedAs		EconomicResource	Economic resource involved in the economic event.
resourceQuantity		Measure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried. This is the quantity that could be used to increment or decrement a resource, depending on the type of resource and resource effect of action.
satisfies		[Satisfaction!]	An intent satisfied fully or partially by an economic event or commitment.
tags		[AnyContext]	Tags/Categories in a taxonomy, linked to resourceClassifiedAs: References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
toResourceInventoriedAs		EconomicResource	Additional economic resource on the economic event when needed by the receiver. Used when a transfer or move, or sometimes other actions, requires explicitly identifying an economic resource on the receiving side.
trace		[ProductionFlowItem!]	
	recurseLimit	Int	
track		[ProductionFlowItem!]	
	recurseLimit	Int	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
triggeredBy		EconomicEvent	References another economic event that implied this economic event, often based on a prior agreement.

EconomicEventPage

A page of Economic Events

Field	Argument	Type	Description
edges		[EconomicEvent!]!	
pageInfo		PageInfo!	
totalCount		Int!	

EconomicEventResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
economicEvent		EconomicEvent!	Details of the newly created event.
economicResource		EconomicResource	Details of any newly created EconomicResource, for events that create new resources.
reciprocalEvents		[EconomicEvent!]!	Any reciprocal events created by found value calculations.

EconomicResource

A resource which is useful to people or the ecosystem.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
accountingQuantity		Measure	The current amount and unit of the economic resource for which the agent has primary rights and responsibilities, sometimes thought of as ownership. This can be either stored or derived from economic events affecting the resource.
classifiedAs		[URI!]!	References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes

Field	Argument	Type	Description
			of categorization or grouping.
conformsTo		ResourceSpecification	The primary resource specification or definition of an existing or potential economic resource. A resource will have only one, as this specifies exactly what the resource is.
containedIn		EconomicResource	Used when a stock economic resource contains items also defined as economic resources.
contains		[EconomicResource !]	Used when a stock economic resource contains units also defined as economic resources.
currentLocation		SpatialThing	The current place an economic resource is located. Could be at any level of granularity, from a town to an address to a warehouse location. Usually mappable.
id		ID!	
image		URI	The uri to an image relevant to the resource, such as a photo, diagram, etc.
lot		ProductBatch	Lot or batch of an economic resource, used to track forward or backwards to all occurrences of resources of that lot. Note more than one resource can be of the same lot.
name		String	An informal or formal textual identifier for an item. Does not imply uniqueness.
note		String	A textual description or comment.
onhandQuantity		Measure	The current amount and unit of the economic resource which is under direct control of the agent. It may be more or less than the accounting quantity. This can be either stored or derived from economic events affecting the resource.
primaryAccountable		Agent	The agent currently with primary rights and responsibilities for the economic resource. It is the

Field	Argument	Type	Description
			agent that is associated with the accountingQuantity of the economic resource.
stage		ProcessSpecification	References the ProcessSpecification of the last process the desired economic resource went through. Stage is used when the last process is important for finding proper resources, such as where the publishing process wants only documents that have gone through the editing process.
state		Action	The state of the desired economic resource (pass or fail), after coming out of a test or review process. Can be derived from the last event if a pass or fail event.
tags		[AnyContext!]	Tags/Categories in a taxonomy, linked to resourceClassifiedAs: References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
trace		[ProductionFlowItem!]	
	recurseLimit	Int	
track		[ProductionFlowItem!]	
	recurseLimit	Int	
trackingIdentifier		String	Sometimes called serial number, used when each item must have a traceable identifier (like a computer). Could also be used for other unique tracking identifiers needed for resources.
unitOfEffort		Unit	The unit used for use or work or cite actions for this resource.

EconomicResourcePage

A page of Economic Resources

Field	Argument	Type	Description
edges		[EconomicResource!]!	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
pageInfo		PageInfo!	
totalCount		Int!	

EconomicResourceResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
economicResource		EconomicResource!	

Follow

Field	Argument	Type	Description
followedCharacter		Character	
followedProfile		Profile	
followerCharacter		Character	
followerProfile		Profile	

Fulfillment

Represents many-to-many relationships between commitments and economic events that fully or partially satisfy one or more commitments.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
effortQuantity		Measure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be cycle counts or other measures of effort or usefulness.
fulfilledBy		EconomicEvent!	The economic event which completely or partially fulfills a commitment.
fulfills		Commitment!	The commitment which is completely or partially fulfilled by an economic event.
id		ID!	
note		String	A textual description or comment.
resourceQuantity		Measure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried.

FulfillmentResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
fulfillment		Fulfillment	

Intent

A planned economic flow which has not been committed to, which can lead to economic events (sometimes through commitments).

Field	Argument	Type	Description
action		Action!	Relates an intent to a verb, such as consume, produce, work, improve, etc.
agreedIn		URI	Reference to an agreement between agents which specifies the rules or policies or calculations which govern this intent.
atLocation		SpatialThing	The place where an intent would occur. Usually mappable.
availableQuantity		Measure	The total quantity of the offered resource available.
canonicalUrl		URI	
deletable		Boolean	The intent can be safely deleted, has no dependent information.
due		DateTime	The time something is expected to be complete.
effortQuantity		Measure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be cycle counts or other measures of effort or usefulness.
finished		Boolean	The intent is complete or not. This is irrespective of if the original goal has been met, and indicates that no more will be done.
hasBeginning		DateTime	The planned beginning of the intent.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
hasEnd		DateTime	The planned end of the intent.
hasPointInTime		DateTime	The planned date/time for the intent. Can be used instead of beginning and end.
id		ID!	
image		URI	The uri to an image relevant to the intent, such as a photo.
inScopeOf		[AccountingScope!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
inputOf		Process	Defines the process to which this intent is an input.
name		String	An informal or formal textual identifier for an intent. Does not imply uniqueness.
note		String	A textual description or comment.
outputOf		Process	Defines the process to which this intent is an output.
provider		Agent	The economic agent from whom the intent is initiated. This implies that the intent is an offer.
publishedIn		[ProposedIntent!]	
receiver		Agent	The economic agent whom the intent is for. This implies that the intent is a request.
resourceClassifiedAs		[URI!]	References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
resourceConformsTo		ResourceSpecification	The primary resource specification or definition of an existing or potential economic resource. A resource will have only one, as this specifies

Field	Argument	Type	Description
			exactly what the resource is.
resourceInventoriedAs		EconomicResource	When a specific EconomicResource is known which can service the Intent, this defines that resource.
resourceQuantity		Measure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried. This is the quantity that could be used to increment or decrement a resource, depending on the type of resource and resource effect of action.
satisfiedBy		[Satisfaction!]	
tags		[AnyContext]	Tags/Categories in a taxonomy, linked to resourceClassifiedAs: References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.

IntentResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
intent		Intent!	

IntentsPage

A page of intents

Field	Argument	Type	Description
edges		[Intent!]!	
pageInfo		PageInfo!	
totalCount		Int!	

LoginResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
currentAccountId		String	
currentUser		User	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
currentUsername		String	
token		String	

Me

Field	Argument	Type	Description
accountId		ID	
flagsForModeration		[Activity]	
	paginate	Paginate	
followed		[Follow]	
	paginate	Paginate	
followers		[Follow]	
	paginate	Paginate	
likeActivities		[Activity]	
	paginate	Paginate	
user		User	
userFeed		[Activity]	
	paginate	Paginate	
userNotifications		[Activity]	
	paginate	Paginate	
users		[User]	

Measure

Semantic meaning for measurements: binds a quantity to its measurement unit. See <http://www.qudt.org/pages/QUDTOverviewPage.html>

Field	Argument	Type	Description
canonicalUrl		URI	Added for CommonsPub
hasNumericalValue		Float!	A number representing the quantity, will be paired with a unit.
hasUnit		Unit!	A unit of measure.
id		ID!	

MeasuresPage

Field	Argument	Type	Description
edges		[Measure!]	
pageInfo		PageInfo	
totalCount		Int	

ObservablePhenomenon

Possible qualitative assessment of an ObservableProperty. (eg. property “contamination” may have phenomenon like “high”, “some”, “none”)

Field	Argument	Type	Description
choiceOf		ObservableProperty	What observable property does this assessment apply to?
formulaQuantifier		Float	A numerical representation of this phenomenon, to be used when automatic analysis is needed (like value calculation formulas).
id		ID!	
label		String!	A name for this phenomenon (eg. high, ripe, organic). Unique to each ObservableProperty.
note		String	A textual description or comment.

ObservablePhenomenonPage

Field	Argument	Type	Description
edges		[ObservablePhenomenon!]	
pageInfo		PageInfo!	
totalCount		Int!	

ObservableProperty

Types of things that can be observed or measured as part of Observation.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
hasChoices		[ObservablePhenomenon!]	
id		ID!	
label		String!	A name for something that can be observed (eg,

Field	Argument	Type	Description
			temperature, weight, contamination...)
note		String	A textual description or comment.

ObservablePropertyPage

Field	Argument	Type	Description
edges		[ObservableProperty!]!	
pageInfo		PageInfo!	
totalCount		Int!	

Observation

An observation event that records the measurement or assesement of an economic resource.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
atLocation		SpatialThing	The place where an observation occurred. Usually mappable.
hasFeatureOfInterest		ObservableObject!	Thing that was observed (like EconomicResource or Agent)
hasResult		ObservableResult!	The result of the observation, which can be one of: - Unit and measurement of what was observed (in the case of quantitative measurements) - Name and other information (using ObservablePhenomenon) about what was observed (in the case of qualitative measurements)
id		ID!	
inScopeOf		[AccountingScope!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
madeBySensor		Observer!	The person (Agent) or a machine like a sensor (EconomicResource or ResourceSpecification) who actually conducted the observation

Field	Argument	Type	Description
note		String	A textual description or comment.
observedDuring		Process	Optionally defines the economic process during which this event occurred
observedProperty		ObservableProperty!	Type of measurement (eg, temperature, weight...).
provider		Agent!	The agent who is providing the observation
resultTime		DateTime!	The date and time at which the observation event.

ObservationPage

Field	Argument	Type	Description
edges		[Observation!]!	
pageInfo		PageInfo!	
totalCount		Int!	

Organization

A formal or informal group, or legal organization.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
agentType		AgentType	
canonicalUrl		String	
commitments		[Commitment!]!	
	filter	agentCommitmentSearchParams	
displayUsername		String	
economicEvents		[EconomicEvent!]!	
	filter	agentEventSearchParams	
id		ID!	
image		URI	The uri to an image relevant to the agent, such as a logo, avatar, photo, etc.
inScopeOf		[AccountingScope!]!	
intents		[Intent!]!	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
	filter	IntentSearchParams	
inventoriedEconomicResources		[EconomicResource!]	
	filter	agentResourceSearchParams	
name		String!	The name that this agent will be referred to by.
note		String	A textual description or comment.
plans		[Plan!]	
	filter	agentPlanSearchParams	
primaryLocation		SpatialThing	The main place an agent is located, often an address where activities occur and mail can be sent. This is usually a mappable geographic location. It also could be a website address, as in the case of agents who have no physical location.
processes		[Process!]	
	filter	agentProcessSearchParams	
proposals		[Proposal!]	
relationships		[AgentRelationship!]	
	roleId	ID	
relationshipsAsObject		[AgentRelationship!]	
	roleId	ID	
relationshipsAsSubject		[AgentRelationship!]	
	roleId	ID	
roles		[AgentRelationshipRole!]	

OrganizationResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
agent		Organization!	

PageInfo

Cursors for pagination

Field	Argument	Type	Description
endCursor		[Cursor!]	Cursor pointing to the last of the results returned, to be used with after query parameter if the backend supports forward pagination.
hasNextPage		Boolean	True if there are more results after endCursor. If unable to be determined, implementations should return true to allow for requerying.
hasPreviousPage		Boolean	True if there are more results before startCursor. If unable to be determined, implementations should return true to allow for requerying.
startCursor		[Cursor!]	Cursor pointing to the first of the results returned, to be used with before query parameter if the backend supports reverse pagination.
totalCount		Int	Returns the total result count, if it can be determined.

Person

A natural person.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
agentType		AgentType	
canonicalUrl		String	
commitments		[Commitment!]	
	filter	agentCommitmentSearchParams	
displayUsername		String	
economicEvents		[EconomicEvent!]	
	filter	agentEventSearchParams	
id		ID!	
image		URI	The uri to an image relevant to the agent, such as a logo, avatar, photo, etc.
intents		[Intent!]	
	filter	IntentSearchParams	
inventoriedEconomicResources		[EconomicResource!]	
	filter	agentResourceSearchParams	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
name		String!	The name that this agent will be referred to by.
note		String	A textual description or comment.
plans		[Plan!]	
	filter	agentPlanSearchParams	
primaryLocation		SpatialThing	The main place an agent is located, often an address where activities occur and mail can be sent. This is usually a mappable geographic location. It also could be a website address, as in the case of agents who have no physical location.
processes		[Process!]	
	filter	agentProcessSearchParams	
proposals		[Proposal!]	
relationships		[AgentRelationship!]	
	roleId	ID	
relationshipsAsObject		[AgentRelationship!]	
	roleId	ID	
relationshipsAsSubject		[AgentRelationship!]	
	roleId	ID	
roles		[AgentRelationshipRole!]	

PersonResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
agent		Person!	

Plan

A logical collection of processes that constitute a body of planned work with defined deliverable(s).

Field	Argument	Type	Description
created		DateTime	The time the plan was made.
deletable		Boolean	The plan is able to be deleted or not.
due		DateTime	The time the plan is expected to be complete.
id		ID!	
inScopeOf		[AccountingScope!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
independentDemands		[Commitment!]	
name		String	An informal or formal textual identifier for a plan. Does not imply uniqueness.
note		String	A textual description or comment.
processes		[Process!]	
	filter	planProcessSearchParams	
refinementOf		Scenario	This plan refines a scenario, making it operational.

PlanResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
plan		Plan	

Post

Field	Argument	Type	Description
activity		Activity	
id		ID	
postContent		PostContent	

PostContent

Field	Argument	Type	Description
htmlBody		String	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
summary		String	
title		String	

Process

An activity that changes inputs into outputs. It could transform or transport economic resource(s).

Field	Argument	Type	Description
basedOn		ProcessSpecification	The definition or specification for a process.
classifiedAs		[URI!]	References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
committedInputs		[Commitment!]	
	action	ID	
committedOutputs		[Commitment!]	
	action	ID	
deletable		Boolean	The process can be safely deleted, has no dependent information.
finished		Boolean	The process is complete or not. This is irrespective of if the original goal has been met, and indicates that no more will be done.
hasBeginning		DateTime	The planned beginning of the process.
hasEnd		DateTime	The planned end of the process.
id		ID!	
inScopeOf		[AccountingScope!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
inputs		[EconomicEvent!]	
	action	ID	
intendedInputs		[Intent!]	
	action	ID	

Field	Argument	Type	Description
	filter	IntentSearchParams	
intendedOutputs		[Intent!]	
	action	ID	
	filter	IntentSearchParams	
name		String!	An informal or formal textual identifier for a process. Does not imply uniqueness.
nestedIn		Scenario	The process with its inputs and outputs is part of the scenario.
nextProcesses		[Process!]	
note		String	A textual description or comment.
outputs		[EconomicEvent!]	
	action	ID	
plannedWithin		Plan	The process with its inputs and outputs is part of the plan.
previousProcesses		[Process!]	
tags		[AnyContext!]	Tags/Categories in a taxonomy, linked to resourceClassifiedAs: References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
trace		[ProductionFlowItem!]	
	recurseLimit	Int	
track		[ProductionFlowItem!]	
	recurseLimit	Int	
unplannedEconomicEvents		[EconomicEvent!]	
	action	ID	
workingAgents		[Agent!]	

ProcessPage

A page of Processes

Field	Argument	Type	Description
edges		[Process!]!	
pageInfo		PageInfo!	
totalCount		Int!	

ProcessResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
process		Process	

ProcessSpecification

Specifies the kind of process.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
id		ID!	
name		String!	An informal or formal textual identifier for the process. Does not imply uniqueness.
note		String	A textual description or comment.

ProcessSpecificationResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
processSpecification		ProcessSpecification	

ProductBatch

A lot or batch, defining a resource produced at the same time in the same way. From DataFoodConsortium vocabulary <https://datafoodconsortium.gitbook.io/dfc-standard-documentation/>.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
batchNumber		String!	The standard unique identifier of the batch.
expiryDate		DateTime	Expiration date of the batch, commonly used for food.
id		ID!	
productionDate		DateTime	Date the batch was produced. Can be derived from the economic event of production.

ProductBatchResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
productBatch		ProductBatch!	

Profile

Field	Argument	Type	Description
name		String	
summary		String	

Proposal

Published requests or offers, sometimes with what is expected in return.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
canonicalUrl		URI	
created		DateTime	The date and time the proposal was created.
creator		Agent	
eligibleLocation		SpatialThing	Location or area where the proposal is valid.
hasBeginning		DateTime	The beginning time of proposal publication.
hasEnd		DateTime	The end time of proposal publication.
id		ID!	
inScopeOf		[AccountingScope!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
name		String	An informal or formal textual identifier for a proposal. Does not imply uniqueness.
note		String	A textual description or comment.
publishedTo		[ProposedTo!]	Which Agent(s) (if any were specified) was this proposed to?
publishes		[ProposedIntent!]	Intent(s) published as part of to this proposal
unitBased		Boolean	This proposal contains unit based quantities, which can be

Field	Argument	Type	Description
			multiplied to create commitments; commonly seen in a price list or e-commerce.

ProposalResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
proposal		Proposal	

ProposalsPage

A page of proposals

Field	Argument	Type	Description
edges		[Proposal!]!	
pageInfo		PageInfo!	
totalCount		Int!	

ProposedIntent

Represents many-to-many relationships between Proposals and Intents, supporting including intents in multiple proposals, as well as a proposal including multiple intents.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
id		ID!	
publishedIn		Proposal!	The published proposal which this intent is part of.
publishes		Intent!	The intent which is part of this published proposal.
reciprocal		Boolean	This is a reciprocal intent of this proposal, not primary. Not meant to be used for intent matching.

ProposedIntentResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
proposedIntent		ProposedIntent	

ProposedTo

An agent to which the proposal is to be published. A proposal can be published to many agents.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
id		ID!	
proposed		Proposal!	The proposal that is published to a specific agent.
proposedTo		Agent!	The agent to which the proposal is published.

ProposedToResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
proposedTo		ProposedTo	

RecipeExchange

Specifies an exchange agreement as part of a recipe.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
id		ID!	
name		String!	An informal or formal textual identifier for a recipe exchange. Does not imply uniqueness.
note		String	A textual description or comment.

RecipeExchangeResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
recipeExchange		RecipeExchange	

RecipeFlow

The specification of a resource inflow to, or outflow from, a recipe process.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
action		Action!	Relates a process input or output to a verb, such as consume, produce, work, modify, etc.
effortQuantity		Measure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be

Field	Argument	Type	Description
			cycle counts or other measures of effort or usefulness.
id		ID!	
note		String	A textual description or comment.
recipeFlowResource		RecipeResource	The resource definition referenced by this flow in the recipe.
recipeInputOf		RecipeProcess	Relates an input flow to its process in a recipe.
recipeOutputOf		RecipeProcess	Relates an output flow to its process in a recipe.
resourceQuantity		Measure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried.

RecipeFlowResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
recipeFlow		RecipeFlow	

RecipeProcess

Specifies a process in a recipe for use in planning from recipe.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
hasDuration		Duration	The planned calendar duration of the process as defined for the recipe batch.
id		ID!	
name		String!	An informal or formal textual identifier for a recipe process. Does not imply uniqueness.
note		String	A textual description or comment.
processClassifiedAs		[URI!]	References a concept in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization.
processConformsTo		ProcessSpecification	The standard specification or definition of a process.

RecipeProcessResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
recipeProcess		RecipeProcess	

RecipeResource

Specifies the resource as part of a recipe, for use in planning from recipe.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
id		ID!	
image		URI	The uri to an image relevant to the entity, such as a photo, diagram, etc.
name		String!	An informal or formal textual identifier for a recipe resource. Does not imply uniqueness.
note		String	A textual description or comment.
resourceClassifiedAs		[URI!]	References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
resourceConformsTo		ResourceSpecification	The primary resource specification or definition of an existing or potential economic resource. A resource will have only one, as this specifies exactly what the resource is.
substitutable		Boolean	Defines if any resource of that type can be freely substituted for any other resource of that type when used, consumed, traded, etc.
unitOfEffort		Unit	The unit used for use action on this resource or work action in the recipe.
unitOfResource		Unit	The unit of inventory used for this resource in the recipe.

RecipeResourceResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
recipeResource		RecipeResource	

Replied

Field	Argument	Type	Description
activity		Activity	
directReplies		[Replied]	
	paginate	Paginate	
post		Post	
postContent		PostContent	
replyToId		ID	
threadId		ID	

ResourceSpecification

Specification of a kind of resource. Could define a material item, service, digital item, currency account, etc. Used instead of a classification when more information is needed, particularly for recipes.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
conformingResources		[EconomicResource!]	
defaultUnitOfEffort		Unit	The default unit used for use or work.
defaultUnitOfResource		Unit	The default unit used for the resource itself.
id		ID!	
image		URI	The uri to an image relevant to the entity, such as a photo, diagram, etc.
name		String!	An informal or formal textual identifier for a type of resource. Does not imply uniqueness.
note		String	A textual description or comment.
resourceClassifiedAs		[URI!]	References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
tags		[AnyContext!]	Tags/Categories in a taxonomy, linked to

Field	Argument	Type	Description
			resourceClassifiedAs: References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.

ResourceSpecificationPage

Field	Argument	Type	Description
edges		[ResourceSpecification!]!	
pageInfo		PageInfo!	
totalCount		Int!	

ResourceSpecificationResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
resourceSpecification		ResourceSpecification	

RootSubscriptionType

Field	Argument	Type	Description
intentCreated		Intent	
	context	String	

Satisfaction

Represents many-to-many relationships between intents and commitments or events that partially or full satisfy one or more intents.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
effortQuantity		Measure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be cycle counts or other measures of effort or usefulness.
id		ID!	
note		String	A textual description or comment.
resourceQuantity		Measure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
satisfiedBy		EventOrCommitment!	A commitment or economic event fully or partially satisfying an intent.
satisfies		Intent!	An intent satisfied fully or partially by an economic event or commitment.

SatisfactionResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
satisfaction		Satisfaction	

Scenario

An estimated or analytical logical collection of higher level processes used for budgeting, analysis, plan refinement, etc.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
definedAs		ScenarioDefinition	The scenario definition for this scenario, for example yearly budget.
hasBeginning		DateTime	The beginning date/time of the scenario, often the beginning of an accounting period.
hasEnd		DateTime	The ending date/time of the scenario, often the end of an accounting period.
id		ID!	
inScopeOf		[AccountingScope!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
name		String!	An informal or formal textual identifier for a scenario. Does not imply uniqueness.
note		String	A textual description or comment.
refinementOf		Scenario	This scenario refines another scenario, often as time moves closer or for more detail.

ScenarioDefinition

The type definition of one or more scenarios, such as Yearly Budget.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
hasDuration		Duration	The duration of the scenario, often an accounting period.
id		ID!	
name		String!	An informal or formal textual identifier for a scenario definition. Does not imply uniqueness.
note		String	A textual description or comment.

ScenarioDefinitionResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
scenarioDefinition		ScenarioDefinition	

ScenarioResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
scenario		Scenario	

Settlement

Represents many-to-many relationships between claim and economic events that fully or partially settle one or more claims.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
effortQuantity		Measure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be cycle counts or other measures of effort or usefulness.
id		ID!	
note		String	A textual description or comment.
resourceQuantity		Measure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
settledBy		EconomicEvent!	The economic event fully or partially settling a claim.
settles		Claim!	A claim which is fully or partially settled by an economic event.

SettlementResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
settlement		Settlement	

SpatialThing

A physical mappable location.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
alt		Float	Altitude.
canonicalUrl		String	
displayUsername		String	
geom		Json	
id		ID!	
inScopeOf		AnyContext	
lat		Float	Latitude.
long		Float	Longitude.
mappableAddress		String	An address that will be recognized as mappable by mapping software.
name		String!	An informal or formal textual identifier for a location. Does not imply uniqueness.
note		String	A textual description or comment.

SpatialThingResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
<code>spatialThing</code>		SpatialThing	

SpatialThingsPage

Field	Argument	Type	Description
<code>edges</code>		[SpatialThing]	
<code>pageInfo</code>		PageInfo	
<code>totalCount</code>		Int	

Tag

A tag could be a category or hashtag or user or community or etc

Field	Argument	Type	Description
<code>canonicalUrl</code>		String	Unique URL (on original instance)
<code>context</code>		AnyContext	The object used as a tag (eg. Category, Geolocation, Hashtag, User...)
<code>displayUsername</code>		String	Unique URL (on original instance)
<code>facet</code>		String	Type of tag (i.e. context)
<code>id</code>		ID	The primary key of the tag
<code>name</code>		String	Name of the tag (derived from its context)
<code>prefix</code>		String	What character is used to trigger this tag (eg. @, #, +)
<code>summary</code>		String	Description of the tag (derived from its context)
<code>tagged</code>		[AnyContext]	Objects that were tagged with this tag

Unit

Defines a unit of measurement, along with its display symbol. From OM2 vocabulary.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
canonicalUrl		URI	Added for CommonsPub
id		ID!	
inScopeOf		AnyContext	
label		String!	A human readable label for the unit, can be language specific.
symbol		String!	A standard display symbol for a unit of measure.

UnitResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
unit		Unit	

UnitsPage

Field	Argument	Type	Description
edges		[Unit!]	
pageInfo		PageInfo	
totalCount		Int	

User

Field	Argument	Type	Description
boostActivities		[Activity]	
	paginate	Paginate	
character		Character	
id		ID	
posts		[Post]	
	paginate	Paginate	
profile		Profile	
userActivities		[Activity]	
	paginate	Paginate	

ValueCalculation

A calculation performed using custom formulas for a certain context.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
action		Action!	Relates a value calculation to a verb, such as consume, produce, work, improve, etc.
formula		String!	
id		ID!	
inScopeOf		[AccountingScope!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
name		String	An informal or formal textual identifier for an item. Does not imply uniqueness.
note		String	A textual description or comment.
resourceClassifiedAs		[URI!]	References a concept in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
resourceConformsTo		ResourceSpecification	Used to filter valueCalculations to find the one that matches the event.
valueAction		Action!	Relates a value calculation to a verb, like action, but for the related event.
valueResourceConformsTo		ResourceSpecification	The resource specification the event will apply to.
valueUnit		Unit!	References the unit used for the event.

ValueCalculationPage

Field	Argument	Type	Description
edges		[ValueCalculation! !]	
pageInfo		PageInfo!	
totalCount		Int!	

ValueCalculationResponse

Field	Argument	Type	Description
valueCalculation		ValueCalculation	

Verb

Field	Argument	Type	Description
verb		String	
verbDisplay		String	

Inputs

ActivityFilters

Field	Type	Description
activityId	ID	
objectId	ID	

AgentCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
image	URI	The uri to an image relevant to the agent, such as a logo, avatar, photo, etc.
name	String!	An informal or formal textual identifier for an agent. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
primaryLocation	ID	(SpatialThing) The main place an agent is located, often an address where activities occur and mail can be sent. This is usually a mappable geographic location. It also could be a website address, as in the case of agents who have no physical location.

AgentRelationshipCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
note	String	A textual description or comment.
object	ID!	(Agent) The object of a relationship between 2 agents. For example, if Mary is

Field	Type	Description
		a member of a group, then the group is the object.
relationship	<u>ID!</u>	(AgentRelationshipRole) The role of an economic relationship that exists between 2 agents, such as member, trading partner.
subject	<u>ID!</u>	(Agent) The subject of a relationship between 2 agents. For example, if Mary is a member of a group, then Mary is the subject.

AgentRelationshipRoleCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
inverseRoleLabel	<u>String</u>	The human readable name of the role, inverse from the object to the subject. For example, 'has member'.
note	<u>String</u>	A textual description or comment.
roleLabel	<u>String!</u>	The human readable name of the role, inverse from the object to the subject. For example, 'is member of'.

AgentRelationshipRoleUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
id	<u>ID!</u>	
inverseRoleLabel	<u>String</u>	The human readable name of the role, inverse from the object to the subject. For example, 'has member'.
note	<u>String</u>	A textual description or comment.
roleLabel	<u>String</u>	The human readable name of the role, inverse from the object to the subject. For example, 'is member of'.

AgentRelationshipUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
id	<u>ID!</u>	

Field	Type	Description
note	String	A textual description or comment.
object	ID	(Agent) The object of a relationship between 2 agents. For example, if Mary is a member of a group, then the group is the object.
relationship	ID	(AgentRelationshipRole) The role of an economic relationship that exists between 2 agents, such as member, trading partner.
subject	ID	(Agent) The subject of a relationship between 2 agents. For example, if Mary is a member of a group, then Mary is the subject.

AgentUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
id	ID!	
image	URI	The uri to an image relevant to the agent, such as a logo, avatar, photo, etc.
name	String	An informal or formal textual identifier for an agent. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
primaryLocation	ID	(SpatialThing) The main place an agent is located, often an address where activities occur and mail can be sent. This is usually a mappable geographic location. It also could be a website address, as in the case of agents who have no physical location.

AgreementCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
created	DateTime!	The date and time the agreement was created.
name	String!	An informal or formal textual identifier for an agreement. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.

AgreementUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
created	DateTime	The date and time the agreement was created.
id	ID!	
name	String	An informal or formal textual identifier for an agreement. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.

AppreciationCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
appreciationOf	ID!	(EconomicEvent) The economic event this appreciation has been given in acknowledgement of.
appreciationWith	ID!	(EconomicEvent) The economic event provided as a gift in this appreciation.
note	String	A textual description or comment.

AppreciationUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
appreciationOf	ID	(EconomicEvent) The economic event this appreciation has been given in acknowledgement of.
appreciationWith	ID	(EconomicEvent) The economic event provided as a gift in this appreciation.
id	ID!	
note	String	A textual description or comment.

CategoryInput

Field	Type	Description
extraInfo	Json	A JSON document containing more info beyond the default fields
facet	String	
name	String!	
parentCategory	ID	
prefix	String	
sameAsCategory	ID	
summary	String	

CharacterFilters

Field	Type	Description
autocomplete	String	
id	ID	
username	String	

CharacterInput

Field	Type	Description
username	String	

ClaimCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
action	ID!	(Action) Relates a claim to a verb, such as consume, produce, work, improve, etc.
agreedIn	URI	Reference to an agreement between agents which specifies the rules or policies or calculations which govern this claim.
created	DateTime	The data on which the claim was made.
due	DateTime	The time the claim is expected to be settled.
effortQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be cycle counts

Field	Type	Description
		or other measures of effort or usefulness.
finished	Boolean	The claim is complete or not. This is irrespective of if the original goal has been met, and indicates that no more will be done.
inScopeOf	[ID!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
provider	ID!	(Agent) The economic agent from whom the claim is initiated.
receiver	ID!	(Agent) The economic agent whom the claim is for.
resourceClassifiedAs	[URI!]	References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
resourceConformsTo	ID	(ResourceSpecification) The primary resource specification or definition of an existing or potential economic resource. A resource will have only one, as this specifies exactly what the resource is.
resourceQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried. This is the quantity that could be used to increment or decrement a resource, depending on the type of resource and resource effect of action.
triggeredBy	ID	(EconomicEvent) The economic event which already occurred which this claim has been made against.

ClaimUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
action	ID	(Action) Relates a claim to a verb, such as consume, produce, work, improve, etc.
agreedIn	URI	Reference to an agreement between agents which specifies the rules or policies or calculations which govern this claim.

Field	Type	Description
created	DateTime	The data on which the claim was made.
due	DateTime	The time the claim is expected to be settled.
effortQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be cycle counts or other measures of effort or usefulness.
finished	Boolean	The claim is complete or not. This is irrespective of if the original goal has been met, and indicates that no more will be done.
id	ID!	
inScopeOf	[ID!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
provider	ID	(Agent) The economic agent from whom the claim is initiated.
receiver	ID	(Agent) The economic agent whom the claim is for.
resourceClassifiedAs	[URI!]	References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
resourceConformsTo	ID	(ResourceSpecification) The primary resource specification or definition of an existing or potential economic resource. A resource will have only one, as this specifies exactly what the resource is.
resourceQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried.
triggeredBy	ID	(EconomicEvent) The economic event which already occurred which this claim has been made against.

CommitmentCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
action	ID!	(Action) Relates a commitment to a verb, such as consume, produce, work, improve, etc.
agreedIn	URI	Reference to an agreement between agents which specifies the rules or policies or calculations which govern this commitment.
atLocation	ID	(SpatialThing) The place where an commitment occurs. Usually mappable.
clauseOf	ID	(Agreement) This commitment is part of the agreement.
due	DateTime	The time something is expected to be complete.
effortQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be cycle counts or other measures of effort or usefulness.
finished	Boolean	The commitment is complete or not. This is irrespective of if the original goal has been met, and indicates that no more will be done.
hasBeginning	DateTime	The planned beginning of the commitment.
hasEnd	DateTime	The planned end of the commitment.
hasPointInTime	DateTime	The planned date/time for the commitment. Can be used instead of beginning and end.
inScopeOf	[ID!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
independentDemandOf	ID	(Plan) Represents a desired deliverable expected from this plan.
inputOf	ID	(Process) Defines the process to which this commitment is an input.

Field	Type	Description
note	String	A textual description or comment.
outputOf	ID	(Process) Defines the process for which this commitment is an output.
provider	ID!	(Agent) The economic agent from whom the commitment is initiated.
receiver	ID!	(Agent) The economic agent whom the commitment is for.
resourceClassifiedAs	[URI!]	References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
resourceConformsTo	ID	(ResourceSpecification) The primary resource specification or definition of an existing or potential economic resource. A resource will have only one, as this specifies exactly what the resource is.
resourceInventoriedAs	ID	(EconomicResource) Exact economic resource involved in the commitment.
resourceQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried.

CommitmentUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
agreedIn	URI	Reference to an agreement between agents which specifies the rules or policies or calculations which govern this commitment.
atLocation	ID	(SpatialThing) The place where an commitment occurs. Usually mappable.
clauseOf	ID	(Agreement) This commitment is part of the agreement.
due	DateTime	The time something is expected to be complete.

Field	Type	Description
effortQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be cycle counts or other measures of effort or usefulness.
finished	Boolean	The commitment is complete or not. This is irrespective of if the original goal has been met, and indicates that no more will be done.
hasBeginning	DateTime	The planned beginning of the commitment.
hasEnd	DateTime	The planned end of the commitment.
hasPointInTime	DateTime	The planned date/time for the commitment. Can be used instead of beginning and end.
id	ID!	
inScopeOf	[ID!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
independentDemandOf	ID	(Plan) Represents a desired deliverable expected from this plan.
inputOf	ID	(Process) Defines the process to which this commitment is an input.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
outputOf	ID	(Process) Defines the process for which this commitment is an output.
provider	ID	(Agent) The economic agent from whom the commitment is initiated.
receiver	ID	(Agent) The economic agent whom the commitment is for.
resourceClassifiedAs	[URI!]	References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.

Field	Type	Description
resourceConformsTo	ID	(ResourceSpecification) The primary resource specification or definition of an existing or potential economic resource. A resource will have only one, as this specifies exactly what the resource is.
resourceInventoriedAs	ID	(EconomicResource) Exact economic resource involved in the commitment.
resourceQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried.

EconomicEventCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
action	ID!	(Action) Relates an economic event to a verb, such as consume, produce, work, improve, etc.
agreedIn	URI	Reference to an agreement between agents which specifies the rules or policies or calculations which govern this economic event.
atLocation	ID	(SpatialThing) The place where an economic event occurs. Usually mappable.
effortQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be cycle counts or other measures of effort or usefulness.
hasBeginning	DateTime	The beginning of the economic event.
hasEnd	DateTime	The end of the economic event.
hasPointInTime	DateTime	The date/time at which the economic event occurred. Can be used instead of beginning and end.
inScopeOf	[ID!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.

Field	Type	Description
inputOf	ID	(Process) Defines the process to which this event is an input.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
outputOf	ID	(Process) Defines the process for which this event is an output.
provider	ID	(Agent) The economic agent from whom the actual economic event is initiated.
realizationOf	ID	(Agreement) This economic event occurs as part of this agreement.
receiver	ID	(Agent) The economic agent whom the actual economic event is for.
resourceClassifiedAs	[URI!]	References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
resourceConformsTo	ID	(ResourceSpecification) The primary resource specification or definition of an existing or potential economic resource. A resource will have only one, as this specifies exactly what the resource is.
resourceInventoriedAs	ID	(EconomicResource) Economic resource involved in the economic event.
resourceQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried. This is the quantity that could be used to increment or decrement a resource, depending on the type of resource and resource effect of action.
tags	[ID!]	Tags/Categories in a taxonomy, linked to resourceClassifiedAs: References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.

Field	Type	Description
toResourceInventoriedAs	ID	(EconomicResource) Additional economic resource on the economic event when needed by the receiver. Used when a transfer or move, or sometimes other actions, requires explicitly identifying an economic resource on the receiving side.
triggeredBy	ID	(EconomicEvent) References another economic event that implied this economic event, often based on a prior agreement.

EconomicEventUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
agreedIn	URI	Reference to an agreement between agents which specifies the rules or policies or calculations which govern this economic event.
id	ID!	
inScopeOf	[ID!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
realizationOf	ID	(Agreement) This economic event occurs as part of this agreement.
triggeredBy	ID	(EconomicEvent) References another economic event that implied this economic event, often based on a prior agreement.

EconomicResourceCreateParams

Input EconomicResource type used when sending events to setup initial resource recordings

Field	Type	Description
conformsTo	ID	(ResourceSpecification) The primary resource specification or definition of an existing or potential economic resource. A resource will have only one, as this specifies exactly what the resource is.
containedIn	ID	(EconomicResource) Used when a stock economic resource contains

Field	Type	Description
		items also defined as economic resources.
currentLocation	ID	(SpatialThing) The current place an economic resource is located. Could be at any level of granularity, from a town to an address to a warehouse location. Usually mappable.
image	URI	The uri to an image relevant to the resource, such as a photo, diagram, etc.
lot	ID	(ProductBatch) Lot or batch of an economic resource, used to track forward or backwards to all occurrences of resources of that lot. Note more than one resource can be of the same lot.
name	String	An informal or formal textual identifier for an item. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
tags	[ID!]	Tags/Categories in a taxonomy, linked to resourceClassifiedAs: References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
trackingIdentifier	String	Sometimes called serial number, used when each item must have a traceable identifier (like a computer). Could also be used for other unique tracking identifiers needed for resources.

EconomicResourceUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
classifiedAs	[URI!]	References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
containedIn	ID	(EconomicResource) Used when a stock economic resource contains items also defined as economic resources.
id	ID!	
image	URI	The uri to an image relevant to the resource, such as a photo, diagram, etc.

Field	Type	Description
note	String	A textual description or comment.
unitOfEffort	ID	(Unit) The unit used for use or work or cite actions for this resource.

FeedFilters

Field	Type	Description
feedName	String	

FulfillmentCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
effortQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be cycle counts or other measures of effort or usefulness.
fulfilledBy	ID!	(EconomicEvent) The economic event which completely or partially fulfills a commitment.
fulfills	ID!	(Commitment) The commitment which is completely or partially fulfilled by an economic event.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
resourceQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried.

FulfillmentUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
effortQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be cycle counts or other measures of effort or usefulness.
fulfilledBy	ID	(EconomicEvent) The economic event which completely or partially fulfills a commitment.
fulfills	ID	(Commitment) The commitment which is completely or partially

Field	Type	Description
		fulfilled by an economic event.
id	ID!	
note	String	A textual description or comment.
resourceQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried.

GeolocationDistance

Field	Type	Description
meters	Int	

GeolocationFilters

Field	Type	Description
distance	GeolocationDistance	
nearAddress	String	
nearPoint	GeolocationPoint	

GeolocationPoint

Field	Type	Description
lat	Float	
long	Float	

IDuration

Mutation input structure for defining time durations.

Field	Type	Description
numericDuration	Float!	A number representing the duration, will be paired with a unit.
unitType	TimeUnit!	A unit of measure.

IMeasure

Mutation input structure for defining measurements. Should be nulled if not present, rather than empty.

Field	Type	Description
hasNumericalValue	Float!	A number representing the quantity, will be paired with a unit.
hasUnit	ID!	(Unit) A unit of measure.

IntentCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
action	String!	(Action) Relates an intent to a verb, such as consume, produce, work, improve, etc.
agreedIn	URI	Reference to an agreement between agents which specifies the rules or policies or calculations which govern this intent.
atLocation	ID	(SpatialThing) The place where an intent occurs. Usually mappable.
availableQuantity	IMeasure	The total quantity of the offered resource available.
due	DateTime	The time something is expected to be complete.
effortQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be cycle counts or other measures of effort or usefulness.
finished	Boolean	The intent is complete or not. This is irrespective of if the original goal has been met, and indicates that no more will be done.
hasBeginning	DateTime	The planned beginning of the intent.
hasEnd	DateTime	The planned end of the intent.
hasPointInTime	DateTime	The planned date/time for the intent. Can be used instead of beginning and end.

Field	Type	Description
image	URI	The uri to an image relevant to the intent, such as a photo.
inScopeOf	[ID!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
inputOf	ID	(Process) Defines the process to which this intent is an input.
name	String	An informal or formal textual identifier for an intent. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
outputOf	ID	(Process) Defines the process to which this intent is an output.
provider	ID	(Agent) The economic agent from whom the intent is initiated. This implies that the intent is an offer.
receiver	ID	(Agent) The economic agent whom the intent is for. This implies that the intent is a request.
resourceClassifiedAs	[URI!]	References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
resourceConformsTo	ID	(ResourceSpecification) The primary resource specification or definition of an existing or potential economic resource. A resource will have only one, as this specifies exactly what the resource is.
resourceInventoriedAs	ID	(EconomicResource) When a specific EconomicResource is known which can service the Intent, this defines that resource.
resourceQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried. This is the quantity that could be used to increment or decrement a resource, depending on the type of resource and resource effect of action.
tags	[ID!]	Tags/Categories in a taxonomy, linked to resourceClassifiedAs:

Field	Type	Description
		References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.

IntentSearchParams

Query parameters for reading Intents related to an Agent

Field	Type	Description
action	[ID]	
agent	[ID]	
atLocation	[ID]	
classifiedAs	[URI]	
endDate	DateTime	
finished	Boolean	
geolocation	GeolocationFilters	
inScopeOf	[ID]	
provider	[ID]	
receiver	[ID]	
searchString	String	
startDate	DateTime	
status	String	
tagIds	[ID]	

IntentUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
action	String	(Action) Relates an intent to a verb, such as consume, produce, work, improve, etc.
agreedIn	URI	Reference to an agreement between agents which specifies the rules or policies or calculations which govern this intent.
atLocation	ID	(SpatialThing) The place where an intent occurs. Usually mappable.

Field	Type	Description
availableQuantity	IMeasure	The total quantity of the offered resource available.
due	DateTime	The time something is expected to be complete.
effortQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be cycle counts or other measures of effort or usefulness.
finished	Boolean	The intent is complete or not. This is irrespective of if the original goal has been met, and indicates that no more will be done.
hasBeginning	DateTime	The planned beginning of the intent.
hasEnd	DateTime	The planned end of the intent.
hasPointInTime	DateTime	The planned date/time for the intent. Can be used instead of beginning and end.
id	ID!	
image	URI	The uri to an image relevant to the intent, such as a photo.
inScopeOf	[ID!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
inputOf	ID	(Process) Defines the process to which this intent is an input.
name	String	An informal or formal textual identifier for an intent. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
outputOf	ID	(Process) Defines the process to which this intent is an output.
provider	ID	(Agent) The economic agent from whom the intent is initiated. This implies that the intent is an offer.
receiver	ID	(Agent) The economic agent whom the intent is for. This implies

Field	Type	Description
		that the intent is a request.
resourceClassifiedAs	[URI!]	References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
resourceConformsTo	ID	(ResourceSpecification) The primary resource specification or definition of an existing or potential economic resource. A resource will have only one, as this specifies exactly what the resource is.
resourceInventoriedAs	ID	(EconomicResource) When a specific EconomicResource is known which can service the Intent, this defines that resource.
resourceQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried. This is the quantity that could be used to increment or decrement a resource, depending on the type of resource and resource effect of action.

ObservablePhenomenonInputParams

Possible qualitative assessment of an ObservableProperty. (eg. property “contamination” may have phenomenon like “high”, “some”, “none”)

Field	Type	Description
choiceOf	ID!	What observable property does this assessment apply to?
formulaQuantifier	Float	A numerical representation of this phenomenon, to be used when automatic analysis is needed (like value calculation formulas). For example, a series of phenomenon of high, medium, low, or none could be assigned formula quantifiers of 100, 50, 10, or 0.
id	ID	
label	String!	A name for this phenomenon (eg. high, ripe, organic). Unique to each ObservableProperty.
note	String	A textual description or comment.

ObservablePropertyInputParams

Types of things that can be observed or measured as part of Observation.

Field	Type	Description
id	ID	
label	String!	A name for something that can be observed (eg, temperature, weight, contamination...)
note	String	A textual description or comment.

ObservationInputParams

Field	Type	Description
atLocation	ID	(SpatialThing) The place where an observation occurred. Usually mappable.
hasFeatureOfInterest	ID!	(EconomicResource or Agent) Thing that was observed
id	ID	
inScopeOf	[ID!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
madeBySensor	ID	(Person or EconomicResource or ResourceSpecification) The person or machine or sensor who actually conducted the observation
note	String	A textual description or comment.
observedDuring	ID	(Process) Optionally defines the economic process during which this event occurred
observedProperty	ID!	(ObservableProperty) Type of measurement (eg, temperature, weight...).
provider	ID	(Person or Organization) The agent who is providing the observation
resultMeasure	IMeasure	Alternatively to resultPhenomenon: Unit and measurement of

Field	Type	Description
		what was observed (only in the case of quantitative measurements)
resultPhenomenon	ID	Alternatively to resultMeasure: (ObservablePhenomenon) Name and other information about what was observed (only in the case of qualitative measurements)
resultTime	DateTime	The date and time at which the observation occurred.

Paginate

Field	Type	Description
after	[Cursor!]	
before	[Cursor!]	
limit	Int	

PlanCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
created	DateTime	The time the plan was made.
due	DateTime	The time the plan is expected to be complete.
name	String!	An informal or formal textual identifier for a plan. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
refinementOf	ID	(Scenario) This plan refines a scenario, making it operational.

PlanUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
created	DateTime	The time the plan was made.
due	DateTime	The time the plan is expected to be complete.

Field	Type	Description
id	ID!	
name	String	An informal or formal textual identifier for a plan. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
refinementOf	ID	(Scenario) This plan refines a scenario, making it operational.

PostContentInput

Field	Type	Description
htmlBody	String	
summary	String	
title	String	

PostFilters

Field	Type	Description
id	ID	

ProcessCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
basedOn	ID	(ProcessSpecification) The definition or specification for a process.
classifiedAs	[URI!]	References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
finished	Boolean	The process is complete or not. This is irrespective of if the original goal has been met, and indicates that no more will be done.
hasBeginning	DateTime	The planned beginning of the process.
hasEnd	DateTime	The planned end of the process.
inScopeOf	[ID!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for

Field	Type	Description
		documenting, accounting, planning.
name	String!	An informal or formal textual identifier for a process. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
plannedWithin	ID	(Plan) The process with its inputs and outputs is part of the plan.
tags	[ID!]	Tags/Categories in a taxonomy, linked to resourceClassifiedAs: References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.

ProcessSpecificationCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
name	String!	An informal or formal textual identifier for the process. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.

ProcessSpecificationUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
id	ID!	
name	String	An informal or formal textual identifier for the process. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.

ProcessUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
basedOn	ID	(ProcessSpecification) The definition or specification for a process.
classifiedAs	[URI!]	References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.

Field	Type	Description
finished	Boolean	The process is complete or not. This is irrespective of if the original goal has been met, and indicates that no more will be done.
hasBeginning	DateTime	The planned beginning of the process.
hasEnd	DateTime	The planned end of the process.
id	ID!	
inScopeOf	[ID!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
name	String	An informal or formal textual identifier for a process. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
plannedWithin	ID	(Plan) The process with its inputs and outputs is part of the plan.

ProductBatchCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
batchNumber	String!	The standard unique identifier of the batch.
expiryDate	DateTime	Expiration date of the batch, commonly used for food.
productionDate	DateTime	Date the batch was produced. Can be derived from the economic event of production.

ProductBatchUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
batchNumber	String	The standard unique identifier of the batch.
expiryDate	DateTime	Expiration date of the batch, commonly used for food.
id	ID!	

Field	Type	Description
productionDate	DateTime	Date the batch was produced. Can be derived from the economic event of production.

ProfileInput

Field	Type	Description
name	String	
summary	String	

ProposalCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
created	DateTime	The date and time the proposal was created.
eligibleLocation	ID	(SpatialThing) The location at which this proposal is eligible.
hasBeginning	DateTime	The beginning time of proposal publication.
hasEnd	DateTime	The end time of proposal publication.
inScopeOf	[ID!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
name	String	An informal or formal textual identifier for a proposal. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
unitBased	Boolean	This proposal contains unit based quantities, which can be multiplied to create commitments; commonly seen in a price list or e-commerce.

ProposalUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
eligibleLocation	ID	(SpatialThing) The location at which this proposal is eligible.

Field	Type	Description
hasBeginning	DateTime	The beginning date/time of proposal publication.
hasEnd	DateTime	The end time of proposal publication.
id	ID!	
inScopeOf	[ID!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
name	String	An informal or formal textual identifier for a proposal. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
unitBased	Boolean	This proposal contains unit based quantities, which can be multiplied to create commitments; commonly seen in a price list or e-commerce.

RecipeExchangeCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
name	String!	An informal or formal textual identifier for a recipe exchange. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.

RecipeExchangeUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
id	ID!	
name	String	An informal or formal textual identifier for a recipe exchange. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.

RecipeFlowCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
action	ID!	(Action) Relates a process input or output to a verb, such as consume, produce, work, modify, etc.
effortQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be cycle counts or other measures of effort or usefulness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
recipeClauseOf	ID	(RecipeExchange) Relates a flow to its exchange agreement in a recipe.
recipeFlowResource	ID!	(RecipeResource) The resource definition referenced by this flow in the recipe.
recipeInputOf	ID	(RecipeProcess) Relates an input flow to its process in a recipe.
recipeOutputOf	ID	(RecipeProcess) Relates an output flow to its process in a recipe.
resourceQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried.
stage	ID	(ProcessSpecification) References the ProcessSpecification of the last process the economic resource went through. Stage is used when the last process is important for finding proper resources, such as where the publishing process wants only documents that have gone through the editing process.
state	String	The state of the desired economic resource (pass or fail), after coming out of a test or review process.

RecipeFlowUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
action	ID	(Action) Relates a process input or output to a verb, such as consume, produce, work, modify, etc.
effortQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be cycle counts

Field	Type	Description
		or other measures of effort or usefulness.
id	ID!	
note	String	A textual description or comment.
recipeFlowResource	ID	(RecipeResource) The resource definition referenced by this flow in the recipe.
recipeInputOf	ID	(RecipeProcess) Relates an input flow to its process in a recipe.
recipeOutputOf	ID	(RecipeProcess) Relates an output flow to its process in a recipe.
resourceQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried.
stage	ID	(ProcessSpecification) References the ProcessSpecification of the last process the economic resource went through. Stage is used when the last process is important for finding proper resources, such as where the publishing process wants only documents that have gone through the editing process.
state	String	The state of the desired economic resource (pass or fail), after coming out of a test or review process.

RecipeProcessCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
hasDuration	IDuration	The planned calendar duration of the process as defined for the recipe batch.
name	String!	An informal or formal textual identifier for a recipe process. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
processClassifiedAs	[URI!]	References a concept in a common taxonomy or other

Field	Type	Description
		classification scheme for purposes of categorization.
processConformsTo	ID!	(ProcessSpecification) The standard specification or definition of a process.

RecipeProcessUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
hasDuration	IDuration	The planned calendar duration of the process as defined for the recipe batch.
id	ID!	
name	String	An informal or formal textual identifier for a recipe process. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
processClassifiedAs	[URI!]	References a concept in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization.
processConformsTo	ID!	(ProcessSpecification) The standard specification or definition of a process.

RecipeResourceCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
image	URI	The uri to an image relevant to the entity, such as a photo, diagram, etc.
name	String!	An informal or formal textual identifier for a recipe resource. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
resourceClassifiedAs	[URI!]	References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.

Field	Type	Description
resourceConformsTo	ID	(ResourceSpecification) The primary resource specification or definition of an existing or potential economic resource. A resource will have only one, as this specifies exactly what the resource is.
substitutable	Boolean	Defines if any resource of that type can be freely substituted for any other resource of that type when used, consumed, traded, etc.
unitOfEffort	ID	(Unit) The unit used for use action on this resource or work action in the recipe.
unitOfResource	ID	(Unit) The unit of inventory used for this resource in the recipe.

RecipeResourceUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
id	ID!	
image	URI	The uri to an image relevant to the entity, such as a photo, diagram, etc.
name	String	An informal or formal textual identifier for a recipe resource. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
resourceClassifiedAs	[URI!]	References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
resourceConformsTo	ID	(ResourceSpecification) The primary resource specification or definition of an existing or potential economic resource. A resource will have only one, as this specifies exactly what the resource is.
substitutable	Boolean	Defines if any resource of that type can be freely substituted for any other resource of that type when used, consumed, traded, etc.
unitOfEffort	ID	(Unit) The unit used for use action on this resource or work action in the recipe.

Field	Type	Description
unitOfResource	ID	(Unit) The unit of inventory used for this resource in the recipe.

ResourceSpecificationCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
defaultUnitOfEffort	ID	(Unit) The default unit used for use or work.
defaultUnitOfResource	ID	(Unit) The default unit used for the resource itself.
image	URI	The uri to an image relevant to the entity, such as a photo, diagram, etc.
name	String!	An informal or formal textual identifier for a type of resource. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
resourceClassifiedAs	[URI!]	References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
tags	[ID!]	Tags/Categories in a taxonomy, linked to resourceClassifiedAs: References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.

ResourceSpecificationUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
defaultUnitOfEffort	ID	(Unit) The default unit used for use or work.
defaultUnitOfResource	ID	(Unit) The default unit used for the resource itself.
id	ID!	
image	URI	The uri to an image relevant to the entity, such as a photo, diagram, etc.
name	String	An informal or formal textual identifier for a type of resource.

Field	Type	Description
		Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
resourceClassifiedAs	[URI!]	References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.
tags	[ID!]	Tags/Categories in a taxonomy, linked to resourceClassifiedAs: References one or more concepts in a common taxonomy or other classification scheme for purposes of categorization or grouping.

SatisfactionCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
effortQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be cycle counts or other measures of effort or usefulness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
resourceQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried.
satisfiedBy	ID!	(Commitment EconomicEvent) A commitment or economic event fully or partially satisfying an intent.
satisfies	ID!	(Intent) An intent satisfied fully or partially by an economic event or commitment.

SatisfactionUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
effortQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be cycle counts or other measures of effort or usefulness.
id	ID!	

Field	Type	Description
note	String	A textual description or comment.
resourceQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried.
satisfiedBy	ID	(Commitment EconomicEvent) A commitment or economic event fully or partially satisfying an intent.
satisfies	ID	(Intent) An intent satisfied fully or partially by an economic event or commitment.

ScenarioCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
definedAs	ID!	(ScenarioDefinition) The scenario definition for this scenario, for example yearly budget.
hasBeginning	DateTime	The beginning date/time of the scenario, often the beginning of an accounting period.
hasEnd	DateTime	The ending date/time of the scenario, often the end of an accounting period.
inScopeOf	[ID!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
name	String!	An informal or formal textual identifier for a scenario. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
refinementOf	ID	(Scenario) This scenario refines another scenario, often as time moves closer or for more detail.

ScenarioDefinitionCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
hasDuration	IDuration	The duration of the scenario, often an accounting period.
name	String	An informal or formal textual identifier for a scenario definition. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.

ScenarioDefinitionUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
hasDuration	IDuration	The duration of the scenario, often an accounting period.
id	ID!	
name	String!	An informal or formal textual identifier for a scenario definition. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.

ScenarioUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
definedAs	ID!	(ScenarioDefinition) The scenario definition for this scenario, for example yearly budget.
hasBeginning	DateTime	The beginning date/time of the scenario, often the beginning of an accounting period.
hasEnd	DateTime	The ending date/time of the scenario, often the end of an accounting period.
id	ID!	
inScopeOf	[ID!]	Grouping around something to create a boundary or context, used for documenting, accounting, planning.
name	String	An informal or formal textual identifier for a scenario. Does not imply uniqueness.

Field	Type	Description
note	String	A textual description or comment.
refinementOf	ID	(Scenario) This scenario refines another scenario, often as time moves closer or for more detail.

SettlementCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
effortQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be cycle counts or other measures of effort or usefulness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.
resourceQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried.
settledBy	ID!	(EconomicEvent) The economic event fully or partially settling a claim.
settles	ID!	(Claim) A claim which is fully or partially settled by an economic event.

SettlementUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
effortQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the work or use or citation effort-based action. This is often a time duration, but also could be cycle counts or other measures of effort or usefulness.
id	ID!	
note	String	A textual description or comment.
resourceQuantity	IMeasure	The amount and unit of the economic resource counted or inventoried.
settledBy	ID	(EconomicEvent) The economic event fully or partially settling a claim.
settles	ID	(Claim) A claim which is fully or partially settled by an economic

Field	Type	Description
		event.

SpatialThingCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
alt	Float	Altitude.
lat	Float	Latitude.
long	Float	Longitude.
mappableAddress	String	An address that will be recognized as mappable by mapping software.
name	String!	An informal or formal textual identifier for a location. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.

SpatialThingUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
alt	Float	Altitude.
id	ID!	
lat	Float	Latitude.
long	Float	Longitude.
mappableAddress	String	An address that will be recognized as mappable by mapping software.
name	String	An informal or formal textual identifier for a location. Does not imply uniqueness.
note	String	A textual description or comment.

UnitCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
inScopeOf	ID	
label	String!	A human readable label for the unit, can be language specific.
symbol	String!	A standard display symbol for a unit of measure.

UnitUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
id	ID!	The primary key of the unit to update.
label	String	A human readable label for the unit, can be language specific.
symbol	String	A standard display symbol for a unit of measure.

ValueCalculationCreateParams

Field	Type	Description
action	ID!	
formula	String!	
inScopeOf	[ID!]	
name	String	
note	String	
resourceClassifiedAs	[URI!]	
resourceConformsTo	ID	
valueAction	ID!	
valueResourceConformsTo	ID	
valueUnit	ID!	

ValueCalculationUpdateParams

Field	Type	Description
action	ID	

Field	Type	Description
formula	String	
id	ID!	
inScopeOf	[ID!]	
name	String	
note	String	
resourceClassifiedAs	[URI!]	
resourceConformsTo	ID	
valueAction	ID	
valueResourceConformsTo	ID	
valueUnit	ID	

agentCommitmentSearchParams

Query parameters for reading Commitments related to an Agent

Field	Type	Description
action	ID	
endDate	DateTime	
finished	Boolean	
searchString	String	
startDate	DateTime	

agentEventSearchParams

Query parameters for reading EconomicEvents related to an Agent

Field	Type	Description
action	ID	
endDate	DateTime	
searchString	String	
startDate	DateTime	

agentPlanSearchParams

Query parameters for reading Plans related to an Agent

Field	Type	Description
finished	Boolean	

Field	Type	Description
searchString	String	

agentProcessSearchParams

Query parameters for reading Processes related to an Agent

Field	Type	Description
finished	Boolean	
searchString	String	

agentResourceSearchParams

Query parameters for reading EconomicResources related to an Agent

Field	Type	Description
page	Int	
resourceClassification	URI	
searchString	String	

planProcessSearchParams

Query parameters for reading Processes related to a Plan

Field	Type	Description
after	DateTime	
before	DateTime	
finished	Boolean	
searchString	String	

Enums

AgentType

Value	Description
Organization	
Person	

TimeUnit

Defines the unit of time measured in a temporal Duration.

Value	Description
day	
hour	
minute	
month	
second	
week	
year	

Scalars

Boolean

The Boolean scalar type represents true or false.

Cursor

An opaque position marker for pagination. Paginated queries return a PageInfo struct with start and end cursors (which are actually lists of Cursor for ...reasons...). You can then issue queries requesting results before the start or after the end cursors to request the previous or next page respectively.

Is actually a string or integer, typically an ID. Can also be include encoded data describing how a query is ordered. May be extended in future.

DateTime

The DateTime scalar type represents a date and time in the UTC timezone. The DateTime appears in a JSON response as an ISO8601 formatted string, including UTC timezone ("Z"). The parsed date and time string will be converted to UTC if there is an offset.

Float

The Float scalar type represents signed double-precision fractional values as specified by [IEEE 754](#).

ID

The ID scalar type represents a unique identifier, often used to refetch an object or as key for a cache. The ID type appears in a JSON response as a String; however, it is not intended to be human-readable. When expected

as an input type, any string (such as "4") or integer (such as 4) input value will be accepted as an ID.

Int

The Int scalar type represents non-fractional signed whole numeric values. Int can represent values between $-(2^{53} - 1)$ and $2^{53} - 1$ since it is represented in JSON as double-precision floating point numbers specified by [IEEE 754](#).

Json

Arbitrary json stored as a string

String

The String scalar type represents textual data, represented as UTF-8 character sequences. The String type is most often used by GraphQL to represent free-form human-readable text.

URI

The URI type simply declares a reference to an external web URL, Holochain entry or other resource.

Interfaces

Agent

A person or group or organization with economic agency.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
agentType		AgentType	
canonicalUrl		String	
commitments		[Commitment!]	
	filter	agentCommitmentSearchParams	
displayUsername		String	
economicEvents		[EconomicEvent!]	
	filter	agentEventSearchParams	
id		ID!	
image		URI	The uri to an image relevant to the agent, such as a logo, avatar, photo, etc.

Field	Argument	Type	Description
intents		[Intent!]	
	filter	IntentSearchParams	
inventoriedEconomicResources		[EconomicResource!]	
	filter	agentResourceSearchParams	
name		String!	An informal or formal textual identifier for an agent. Does not imply uniqueness.
note		String	A textual description or comment.
plans		[Plan!]	
	filter	agentPlanSearchParams	
primaryLocation		SpatialThing	The main place an agent is located, often an address where activities occur and mail can be sent. This is usually a mappable geographic location. It also could be a website address, as in the case of agents who have no physical location.
processes		[Process!]	
	filter	agentProcessSearchParams	
proposals		[Proposal!]	
relationships		[AgentRelationship!]	
	roleId	ID	
relationshipsAsObject		[AgentRelationship!]	
	roleId	ID	
relationshipsAsSubject		[AgentRelationship!]	
	roleId	ID	
roles		[AgentRelationshipRole!]	

Unions

AccountingScope

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

A boundary or context grouped around some other record- used for documenting, accounting, planning. ##
extended for Bonfire (default was Person | Organization)

Type	Description
Category	A category (eg. tag in a taxonomy)
Organization	A formal or informal group, or legal organization.
Person	A natural person.
Tag	A tag could be a category or hashtag or user or community or etc

AnyCharacter

Any type of character (eg. Category, Thread, Geolocation, etc), actor (eg. User/Person), or agent (eg. Organisation)

Type	Description
Category	A category (eg. tag in a taxonomy)
SpatialThing	A physical mappable location.
User	

AnyContext

Any type of known object

Type	Description
Activity	
Category	A category (eg. tag in a taxonomy)
EconomicEvent	An observed economic flow, as opposed to a flow planned to happen in the future. This could reflect a change in the quantity of an economic resource. It is also defined by its behavior in relation to the economic resource (see Action)
Follow	
Intent	A planned economic flow which has not been committed to, which can lead to economic events (sometimes through commitments).
Post	
Process	An activity that changes inputs into outputs. It could transform or transport economic resource(s).
SpatialThing	A physical mappable location.
Tag	A tag could be a category or hashtag or user or community or etc
User	

EventOrCommitment

Type	Description
Commitment	A planned economic flow that has been promised by an agent to another agent.
EconomicEvent	An observed economic flow, as opposed to a flow planned to happen in the future. This could reflect a change in the quantity of an economic resource. It is also defined by its behavior in relation to the economic resource (see Action)

ObservableObject

Things that can be observed.

Type	Description
EconomicResource	A resource which is useful to people or the ecosystem.
Organization	A formal or informal group, or legal organization.
Person	A natural person.

ObservableResult

Can contain either a unit+measure or a qualitative assessment.

Type	Description
Measure	Semantic meaning for measurements: binds a quantity to its measurement unit. See http://www.qudt.org/pages/QUDToverviewPage.html
ObservablePhenomenon	Possible qualitative assessment of an ObservableProperty. (eg. property “contamination” may have phenomenon like “high”, “some”, “none”)

Observer

Agent (usually a person) or machine like a sensor that conducts observations.

Type	Description
EconomicResource	A resource which is useful to people or the ecosystem.
Organization	A formal or informal group, or legal organization.
Person	A natural person.
ResourceSpecification	Specification of a kind of resource. Could define a material item, service, digital item, currency account, etc. Used instead of a classification when more information is needed, particularly for recipes.

ProductionFlowItem

Type	Description
EconomicEvent	An observed economic flow, as opposed to a flow planned to happen in the future. This could reflect a change in the quantity of an economic resource. It is also defined by its behavior in relation to the economic resource (see Action)
EconomicResource	A resource which is useful to people or the ecosystem.
Process	An activity that changes inputs into outputs. It could transform or transport economic resource(s).

7.1.2 ReflowOS APIRoom API

POST/get-objects

Get records of types: EconomicResource, EconomicEvent, Process, Agent

Parameters

No parameters

Request body

```
{
  "ids*": [
    {
      "type": "IDstring",
      "pattern": "^[0-9A-HJKMNP-TV-Z]{26}$",
      "description": "26 characters of Crockford's Base32-encoded string https://www.crockford.com/base32.html"
    }
  ],
  "unwind": {
    "type": "boolean",
    "default": "false",
    "description": "strips out the data key from the outermost returned object"
  }
}
```

example: `OrderedMap { "ids": List ["01G1AXXCECBY03TJW94314807G", "01G1AY1YNE3P6W36Q8P65QNP56", "01G1AY2FJS2BCVA88CMJZDN5EX"], "unwind": true }`

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	list of found records, if any	

Code	Description	Links
	Media type: application/json	

Controls Accept header.

	<pre> { if unwind is true[title: if unwind is true { anyOf -> EconomicResource{...} EconomicEvent{...} Process{...} Agent{...} }] oneOf -> if unwind is false, default{ data [[anyOf -> EconomicResource{...} EconomicEvent{...} Process{...} Agent{...}]]</pre>	No links
--	---	----------

POST/trace

Get the related trace data of one of the types: EconomicResource, EconomicEvent, Process

Parameters

No parameters

Request body

	<pre> {</pre>
id*	<p>IDstring pattern: <code>^[0-9A-HJKMNP-TV-Z]{26}\$</code></p> <p>26 characters of Crockford's Base32-encoded string https://www.crockford.com/base32.html</p>
recurseLimit	<p>number(Integer) default: 2 minimum: 1 maximum: 1000</p>
unwind	<p>boolean default: false</p>

	strips out the data key from the outer most returned object
--	---

}

example: `OrderedMap { "id": "01G1AXXCECBY03TJW94314807G", "recurseLimit": 2, "unwind": true }`

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	list of found records, if any Media type:application/json	

Controls Accept header.

	<pre> if unwind is true[title: if unwind is true { EconomicResource{...} anyOf -> EconomicEvent{...} Process{...} }] oneOf -> if unwind is false, default{ [{ data EconomicResource{...} anyOf -> EconomicEvent{...} Process{...} }] } </pre>
--	--

POST/track

Get the related trace data of one of the types: EconomicResource, EconomicEvent, Process

Parameters

No parameters

Request body

id*	IDstring pattern: <code>^[0-9A-HJKMNP-TV-Z]{26}\$</code>
-----	---

	26 characters of Crockford's Base32-encoded string https://www.crockford.com/base32.html
recurseLimit	number(\$integer) default: 2 minimum: 1 maximum: 1000
unwind	boolean default: false strips out the data key from the outer most returned object

}

example: `OrderedMap { "id": "01G1AXXCECBY03TJW94314807G", "recurseLimit": 2, "unwind": true }`

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	list of found records, if any Media type: application/json	

Controls Accept header.

{

oneOf ->	<pre> if unwind is true[title: if unwind is true { EconomicResource{...} } anyOf -> EconomicEvent{...} Process{...} }] if unwind is false, default{ [{ data anyOf -> EconomicResource{...} EconomicEvent{...} Process{...} }] } </pre>

}

Schemas

IDstring

pattern: `^[0-9A-HJKMNP-TV-Z]{26}$`

26 characters of Crockford's Base32-encoded string <https://www.crockford.com/base32.html>

SpatialThing{

id	IDstring pattern: <code>^[0-9A-HJKMNP-TV-Z]{26}\$</code> 26 characters of Crockford's Base32-encoded string https://www.crockford.com/base32.html
name	string
note	string nullable: true
mappleAddress	string nullable: true
lat	number(\$float) nullable: true
alt	number(\$float) nullable: true
long	number(\$float) nullable: true

}

Action{

id	IDstring pattern: <code>^[0-9A-HJKMNP-TV-Z]{26}\$</code> 26 characters of Crockford's Base32-encoded string https://www.crockford.com/base32.html
----	---

}

Unit{

id	IDstring pattern: <code>^[0-9A-HJKMNP-TV-Z]{26}\$</code> 26 characters of Crockford's Base32-encoded string https://www.crockford.com/base32.html
label	string
symbol	string

}

Measure{

hasNumericalValue	number(\$float)
hasUnit	Unit{
	id IDstring

	pattern: <code>^[0-9A-HJKMNP-TV-Z]{26}\$</code> 26 characters of Crockford's Base32-encoded string https://www.crockford.com/base32.html
label	string
symbol	string
	}

EconomicResource{

__typename	string pattern: <code>^EconomicResource\$</code>
id	IDstring pattern: <code>^[0-9A-HJKMNP-TV-Z]{26}\$</code> 26 characters of Crockford's Base32-encoded string https://www.crockford.com/base32.html
resourceName	string
note	string nullable: true
primaryAccountable	Agent{...}
accountingQuantity	Measure{...}
onhandQuantity	Measure{...}
currentLocation	SpatialThing{...}
trackingIdentifier	string nullable: true
	}

EconomicEvent{

__typename	string pattern: <code>^EconomicEvent\$</code>				
id	IDstring pattern: <code>^[0-9A-HJKMNP-TV-Z]{26}\$</code> 26 characters of Crockford's Base32-encoded string https://www.crockford.com/base32.html				
note	string nullable: true				
provider	Agent{...}				
receiver	Agent{...}				
action	Action{...}				
resourceQuantity	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>hasNumericalValue</td> <td>number(\$float)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>hasUnit</td> <td>Unit{...}</td> </tr> </table> nullable: true	hasNumericalValue	number(\$float)	hasUnit	Unit{...}
hasNumericalValue	number(\$float)				
hasUnit	Unit{...}				
effortQuantity	{				

	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>hasNumericalValue</td> <td>number(\$float)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>hasUnit</td> <td>Unit{...}</td> </tr> </table>	hasNumericalValue	number(\$float)	hasUnit	Unit{...}																				
hasNumericalValue	number(\$float)																								
hasUnit	Unit{...}																								
] nullable: true																								
resourceClassifiedAs	[nullable: true string]																								
resourceInventoriedAs	<table border="1"> <tr> <td colspan="2">{</td> </tr> <tr> <td>__typename</td> <td>string pattern: ^EconomicResource\$</td> </tr> <tr> <td>id</td> <td>IDstring pattern: ^[0-9A-HJKMNP-TV-Z]{26}\$ 26 characters of Crockford's Base32-encoded string https://www.crockford.com/base32.html</td> </tr> <tr> <td>resourceName</td> <td>string</td> </tr> <tr> <td>note</td> <td>string nullable: true</td> </tr> <tr> <td>primaryAccountable</td> <td>Agent{...}</td> </tr> <tr> <td>accountingQuantity</td> <td>Measure{...}</td> </tr> <tr> <td>onhandQuantity</td> <td>Measure{...}</td> </tr> <tr> <td>currentLocation</td> <td>SpatialThing{...}</td> </tr> <tr> <td>trackingIdentifier</td> <td>string nullable: true</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="2">}</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="2">nullable: true</td> </tr> </table>	{		__typename	string pattern: ^EconomicResource\$	id	IDstring pattern: ^[0-9A-HJKMNP-TV-Z]{26}\$ 26 characters of Crockford's Base32-encoded string https://www.crockford.com/base32.html	resourceName	string	note	string nullable: true	primaryAccountable	Agent{...}	accountingQuantity	Measure{...}	onhandQuantity	Measure{...}	currentLocation	SpatialThing{...}	trackingIdentifier	string nullable: true	}		nullable: true	
{																									
__typename	string pattern: ^EconomicResource\$																								
id	IDstring pattern: ^[0-9A-HJKMNP-TV-Z]{26}\$ 26 characters of Crockford's Base32-encoded string https://www.crockford.com/base32.html																								
resourceName	string																								
note	string nullable: true																								
primaryAccountable	Agent{...}																								
accountingQuantity	Measure{...}																								
onhandQuantity	Measure{...}																								
currentLocation	SpatialThing{...}																								
trackingIdentifier	string nullable: true																								
}																									
nullable: true																									
toResourceInventoriedAs	<table border="1"> <tr> <td colspan="2">{</td> </tr> <tr> <td>__typename</td> <td>string pattern: ^EconomicResource\$</td> </tr> <tr> <td>id</td> <td>IDstring pattern: ^[0-9A-HJKMNP-TV-Z]{26}\$ 26 characters of Crockford's Base32-encoded string https://www.crockford.com/base32.html</td> </tr> <tr> <td>resourceName</td> <td>string</td> </tr> <tr> <td>note</td> <td>string nullable: true</td> </tr> <tr> <td>primaryAccountable</td> <td>Agent{...}</td> </tr> <tr> <td>accountingQuantity</td> <td>Measure{...}</td> </tr> <tr> <td>onhandQuantity</td> <td>Measure{...}</td> </tr> <tr> <td>currentLocation</td> <td>SpatialThing{...}</td> </tr> <tr> <td>trackingIdentifier</td> <td>string nullable: true</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="2">}</td> </tr> <tr> <td colspan="2">nullable: true</td> </tr> </table>	{		__typename	string pattern: ^EconomicResource\$	id	IDstring pattern: ^[0-9A-HJKMNP-TV-Z]{26}\$ 26 characters of Crockford's Base32-encoded string https://www.crockford.com/base32.html	resourceName	string	note	string nullable: true	primaryAccountable	Agent{...}	accountingQuantity	Measure{...}	onhandQuantity	Measure{...}	currentLocation	SpatialThing{...}	trackingIdentifier	string nullable: true	}		nullable: true	
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note	string nullable: true																								
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Process{

__typename	string pattern: ^Process\$	
id	IDstring pattern: ^[0-9A-HJKMNP-TV-Z]{26}\$ 26 characters of Crockford's Base32-encoded string https://www.crockford.com/base32.html	
processName	string	
note	string nullable: true	
inputs	[nullable: true EconomicEvent{	
	__typename	string pattern: ^EconomicEvent\$
	id	IDstring pattern: ^[0-9A-HJKMNP-TV-Z]{26}\$ 26 characters of Crockford's Base32-encoded string https://www.crockford.com/base32.html
	note	string nullable: true
	provider	Agent{...}
	receiver	Agent{...}
	action	Action{ IDstring pattern: ^[0-9A-HJKMNP-TV-Z]{26}\$ id 26 characters of Crockford's Base32-encoded string https://www.crockford.com/base32.html }
	resourceQuantity	{ hasNumericalValue number(\$float) hasUnit Unit{...} } nullable: true
	effortQuantity	{ hasNumericalValue number(\$float) hasUnit Unit{...} } nullable: true
	resourceClassifiedAs	[nullable: true string]
resourceInventoriedAs	{ __typename string pattern: ^EconomicResource\$ id IDstring	

	<pre> pattern: ^[0-9A-HJKMNP-TV-Z]{26}\$ 26 characters of Crockford's Base32-encoded string https://www.crockford.com/base32.html resourceName string note string nullable: true primaryAccountable Agent{...} accountingQuantity Measure{...} onhandQuantity Measure{...} currentLocation SpatialThing{...} trackingIdentifier string nullable: true } nullable: true </pre>
	<pre> { __typename string pattern: ^EconomicResource\$ IDstring pattern: ^[0-9A-HJKMNP-TV-Z]{26}\$ id 26 characters of Crockford's Base32-encoded string https://www.crockford.com/base32.html resourceName string note string nullable: true primaryAccountable Agent{...} accountingQuantity Measure{...} onhandQuantity Measure{...} currentLocation SpatialThing{...} trackingIdentifier string nullable: true } nullable: true </pre>
outputs	[...]
	}}

Agent{

__typename	string pattern: ^Agent\$
id	IDstring pattern: ^[0-9A-HJKMNP-TV-Z]{26}\$ 26 characters of Crockford's Base32-encoded string https://www.crockford.com/base32.html
name	string

displayUsername	string
note	string nullable: true

}

7.2 ODD APIs & templates

7.2.1 ODD Piveau Scheduler API

GET/triggers

Map of pipe ids and triggers

Get a list of pipe ids and scheduled triggers.

Parameters

No parameters

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	The map of pipe ids and triggers Media type: application/json	

Controls Accept header.

{		
< * >:	[[anyOf -> IntervalTrigger{...} CronTrigger{...} SpecificTrigger{...}]]	No links
}		

PUT/triggers

Bulk update

Bulk update of all triggers

Parameters

- No parameters

Request body

The trigger objects

```
{
  [
    < * >: [
      IntervalTrigger{...}
      CronTrigger{...}
      SpecificTrigger{...}
    ]
  ]
}
```

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Triggers updated successfully.	<i>No links</i>

GET/triggers/{pipeID}

Get triggers

Returns all triggers for pipe with pipeId.

Parameters

Name	Description
pipeId * string (path)	Id of the pipe to trigger.

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	The trigger objects Media type: application/json	

Controls Accept header.

<pre> [{ IntervalTrigger{...} } anyOf -> { CronTrigger{...} SpecificTrigger{...} }] </pre>	<i>No links</i>	
404	Pipe not found.	<i>No links</i>

PUT/triggers/{pipeId}

Create or update triggers

Create or update triggers for pipe with pipeId.

Parameters

Name	Description
pipeId * string (path)	Id of the pipe to trigger.

Request body

The trigger objects

```

[
  {
    ImmediateTrigger{...}
  }
  anyOf ->
  {
    IntervalTrigger{...}
    CronTrigger{...}
    SpecificTrigger{...}
  }
]

```

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Triggers updated successfully.	<i>No links</i>
201	Triggers created successfully.	<i>No links</i>

Code	Description	Links
404	Pipe not found.	<i>No links</i>

DELETE/triggers/{pipeId}

Delete triggers

Delete previously created triggers.

Parameters

Name	Description
pipeId * string (path)	Id of the pipe to trigger.

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Triggers successfully deleted.	<i>No links</i>
404	Pipe not found.	<i>No links</i>

GET/triggers/{pipeId}/{triggerId}/{status}

Set status

Set status of a trigger.

Parameters

Name	Description
pipeId * string (path)	Id of the pipe to trigger.
triggerId * string (path)	Id of the trigger.
status * string (path)	Status to set for the trigger.

Name	Description
	<i>Available values : enable, disable</i>

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Trigger status successfully set. The body contains the old status. Media type: text/plain	

Controls Accept header.

string	<i>No links</i>	
404	Pipe or Trigger not found. Body contains more details.	<i>No links</i>
409	Status already set or unknown.	<i>No links</i>

Schemas

Trigger{

description:	A trigger object.
id*	string A unique identifier within the scope of the pipe
status*	string Indicating the status of the trigger Enum: [enabled, disabled]
configs	{...}

}

ImmediateTrigger{

description:	A trigger that is triggered immediately
id*	string A unique identifier within the scope of the pipe
status*	string MUST BE enabled Enum: [enabled, disabled, enabled]
configs	{...}

}

IntervalTrigger{

description:	Am interval based trigger
id*	string A unique identifier within the scope of the pipe
status*	string Indicating the status of the trigger Enum: Array [2]
configs	{...}
interval*	{ value* integer unit* string }
next	string(\$date-time) The first trigger

}

CronTrigger{

description:	A cron based trigger definition
id*	string A unique identifier within the scope of the pipe
status*	string Indicating the status of the trigger Enum: [enabled, disabled]
configs	{...}
cron*	string The cron systax
next	string(\$date-time) The first trigger

}

SpecificTrigger{

description:	A list of specific trigger times
id*	string A unique identifier within the scope of the pipe
status*	string Indicating the status of the trigger Enum: [enabled, disabled]
configs	{...}
specific*	[List of specific date and time triggers string(\$date-time)]

```
}
```

7.2.2 ODD PipeObject JSON template

```
{
  "header": {
    "name": "PipeName",
    "transport": "payload",
    "version": "2.0.0"
  },
  "body": {
    "segments": [
      {
        "header": {
          "name": "piveau-consus-importing-json",
          "segmentNumber": 1,
          "title": "Importing GRAPHQL",
          "processed": false
        },
        "body": {
          "config": {
            "address": "GraphQL-Query-URL",
            "inputFormat": "application/graphql",
            "alternativeLoad": false,
            "tableName": "name of table",
            "replaceTable": true
          }
        }
      },
      {
        "header": {
          "name": "piveau-consus-transforming-js",
          "segmentNumber": 2,
          "title": "Transforming js",
          "processed": false
        },
        "body": {
          "config": {
            "single": true,
            "scriptType": "repository",
            "repository": {
              "uri": "https://uri-to-transformation-script-repo",
              "branch": "main",
              "script": "path/to/TransformationScript.js",
              "username": "username",
              "token": "token"
            }
          }
        }
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "header": {
```



```
"name": "piveau-consus-exporting-superset-pilot-name",  
"segmentNumber": 3,  
"title": "Exporting hub"  
}  
}  
]  
}  
}  
}
```

